

Bioprocessed plant protein diets enriched with hydrolyzed microalgae-grape marc extracts improve growth and welfare in *Sparus aurata* juveniles

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the effects of an enzymatically hydrolyzed plant-based diet supplemented with a nutraceutical compound on growth performance, metabolism, welfare, and hepatic and intestinal health in *Sparus aurata*. Juvenile fish (13–14 g) were fed *ad libitum* for 84 days with three experimental diets: a control diet (CT; 20% fishmeal), a plant-protein-based diet in which hydrolyzed plant proteins replaced 60% of fishmeal (PP), and the same plant-based diet supplemented with 2% of a microalgae- and grape marc-derived nutraceutical (GG; *LB-GreenGrape*). Fish fed the PP diet exhibited reduced final weight and length, likely due to differences in feed intake and feed efficiency. These growth impairments were associated with elevated plasma Gh levels, reduced Igf1 levels, and a decreased Igf1/Gh ratio, together with evidence of hormonal uncoupling at the molecular level. In addition, the PP group showed increased expression of *hsd11b2* and *nr3c1* in the head kidney, suggesting a compensatory response to nutritional impairment. At the hepatic level, no signs of tissue damage were observed; however, hepatocyte area increased significantly in PP-fed fish. In addition, the intestinal length index was reduced in these fish compared to the CT group, possibly due to the enzymatic pre-treatment of plant proteins. In contrast, supplementation with *LB-GreenGrape* partially restored growth performance and normalized key endocrine and molecular alterations, including the Igf1/Gh ratio and hormonal coupling. The nutraceutical also attenuated the upregulation of *hsd11b2* and *nr3c1*, while reducing *star* expression, indicating modulation of steroidogenic activity in the interrenal tissue. Both hepatocyte area and intestinal length remained comparable to those of the CT group. Notably, only the GG group exhibited a significant increase in goblet cell density in the anterior intestine, suggesting enhanced mucosal defense capacity. Additionally, nutraceutical supplementation reduced feed production costs relative to the unsupplemented plant-based diet, although both diets remained more expensive than the control (CT). Overall, most physiological, metabolic, and molecular parameters remained stable across diets, supporting the effectiveness of enzymatically treated plant-based formulations. Supplementation with *LB-GreenGrape* further enhanced growth performance and physiological resilience without compromising health, contributing to more sustainable aquaculture feeds.

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1. Introduction

Nutritional status exerts a significant influence on growth regulation in fish, a complex process governed by an interconnected network of endocrine, molecular, and physiological mechanisms (Picha et al., 2008). Growth hormone (Gh) acts as a central endocrine regulator in vertebrates, promoting somatic growth by binding to specific receptors (Ghr1 and Ghr2) and stimulating the production of insulin-like growth factors (Igf), primarily Igf1, which exert anabolic effects on metabolism and cell proliferation (Reinecke et al., 2005). Nutritional imbalances can activate physiological stress responses that disrupt metabolic homeostasis and negatively affect growth by altering the Gh/Igf axis and its downstream signaling pathways (Pérez-Sánchez et al., 1995). Chronic stress, which may be triggered by poor nutritional status, can suppress Igf1 expression and reduce tissue sensitivity to Gh, ultimately impairing growth performance (Canosa and Bertucci, 2023).

In this context, appropriate dietary management is essential not only for optimizing growth but also for promoting fish welfare, mitigating stress responses, and supporting physiological resilience. One of the major challenges in achieving this balance arises from the increasing use of plant-based ingredients in aquafeeds (Colombo, 2020), a trend that has intensified in recent decades (Le Boucher et al., 2011). However, their inclusion has been limited by several constraints, including low digestibility, poor nutritional quality, imbalances or deficiencies in essential amino acids, and the presence of antinutritional factors (ANF) (Desai et al., 2012). These ANF, primarily synthesized by plants, interfere with nutrient utilization, metabolic and gastrointestinal functions, and host immunity, thereby affecting key aspects of fish production (Francis et al., 2001; Le Boucher et al., 2011; Reverter et al., 2021; Ahmad et al., 2022; Idenyi et al., 2022; Caderno et al., 2025). Common examples include saponins, lectins, oligosaccharides, phytates, and glucosinolates (Krogdahl et al., 2010; Midhun and Arun, 2023). Consequently, feed formulations containing these ingredients require optimization, particularly for carnivorous fish species, which are less capable of efficiently digesting and utilizing plant-derived nutrients (Colombo, 2020). Within this framework, *Sparus aurata*, commonly known as gilthead seabream, is one of the most important marine species in Mediterranean aquaculture due to its high market value and strong consumer demand (APROMAR, 2024). Nevertheless, as a carnivorous species, it is particularly sensitive to plant-based diets (Diógenes et al., 2019), making it an excellent model for evaluating novel functional feeds.

To improve the quality of plant-based diets, various processing approaches have been developed to reduce ANF and limit their negative effects (Gule and Geremew, 2022; Cao et al., 2024). These include dry and wet heating, water extraction, fermentation, enzymatic treatments, coating, microencapsulation, and the use of feed additives, which are widely applied in aquafeeds (Krogdahl et al., 2010; Prabu et al., 2017; Sarker, 2023). Moreover, the integration of advanced processing strategies, such as enzymatic biotechnological treatment of plant ingredients and the inclusion of functional ingredients, can synergistically enhance the nutritional and functional value of aquaculture diets (Vizcaíno et al., 2024), providing benefits beyond basic nutrition (Kaur and Das, 2011; Perera et al., 2020; Shinde et al., 2024; Caderno et al., 2025; Molina-Roque et al., 2025). These improvements help overcome the limitations associated with ingredients of low digestible energy content and support the development of novel production models aimed at improving both the quality and sustainability of farmed species (Encarnação, 2016; Hossain et al., 2024).

Building on these advances, the incorporation of novel functional ingredients into aquafeeds has gained considerable attention. Among these, microalgae have emerged as a promising option due to their high nutritional value, including elevated crude protein content, a wide range of bioactive compounds, and strong antioxidant capacity (Hua et al., 2019; Nagarajan et al., 2021; Huy et al., 2022; Idenyi et al., 2022). Furthermore, microalgae have been shown to improve the fatty acid

profile of fish by enhancing the omega-3/omega-6 ratio, increasing total polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA), and promoting the accumulation of long-chain PUFA (Ahmad et al., 2022). Other alternative raw materials, such as wine by-products, have also been explored as potential functional ingredients (Martínez-Antequera et al., 2023; Quagliardi et al., 2024). The use of these residues may help mitigate environmental pollution and reduce greenhouse gas emissions, thereby promoting the circular economy (Contreras et al., 2022). In particular, grape marc is rich in fatty acids, proteins, fiber, minerals, and bioactive compounds, including polyphenols and antioxidants, making it a highly suitable candidate for nutritional supplementation (Barbacariu et al., 2024). However, despite their nutritional and functional potential, both microalgae and grape marc may present limitations related to nutrient availability and digestibility. These constraints are mainly associated with the rigidity of their cell walls and the presence of ANF, such as complex polysaccharides or phenolic compounds (Ahmad et al., 2022; Sarker, 2023; Barbacariu et al., 2024). Consequently, even when used as sources of functional compounds, these ingredients may require prior biotechnological processing, such as enzymatic hydrolysis or fermentation, to improve digestibility, reduce undesirable components, and maximize their bioactive potential. This underscores the importance of optimizing not only plant-based diets themselves but also the biotechnological processing of raw materials used to produce nutraceutical compounds, in order to develop more effective and sustainable aquaculture feeds.

This study adopts a comprehensive and preliminary approach, integrating physiological, biochemical, and molecular endpoints to evaluate the impact of functional diets and to better understand the systemic effects of dietary interventions in aquaculture species. In this context, the study assessed the effects of a hydrolyzed plant protein-rich diet, supplemented with the nutraceutical compound *LB-Green_{Grape}*, on intermediary metabolism, the somatotrophic axis, the stress response, and histological parameters in juvenile gilthead seabream (*S. aurata*). *LB-Green_{Grape}* is derived from a blend of hydrolyzed microalgae species and *Albariño* grape marc extract, serving as a source of bioactive peptides, polyunsaturated fatty acids, carotenoids, and antioxidant compounds. The functional ingredient was developed by *LifeBioencapsulation* S.L. and *I-grape* S.L., spin-offs from the University of Almería and the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain), respectively.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Ethics

Fish were handled and maintained in accordance with the guidelines for experimental procedures involving animals established by the Ethics and Animal Welfare Committee of the University of Cádiz, as well as with Spanish regulations (RD 53/2013 and RD 118/2021) and European Union legislation (Directive 2010/63/EU). The experimental protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Andalusian Regional Government (Junta de Andalucía; reference number 23/10/2019/176).

2.2. Diets and feeding protocol

Experimental groups were established in triplicate according to the diet provided ($n = 90$ fish per experimental group, $n = 30$ fish per tank). Three isonitrogenous (47% dry weight basis) and isolipidic (18% dry weight basis) diets (Table 1 and Table 2) were manufactured at the CEIMAR-University of Almería facilities (*Servicio de Piensos Experimentales*, Almería, Spain; <https://www.ual.es/universidad/serviciosgerales/stecnicos/perifericos-convenio/piensos-experimentales>). The dietary treatments were as follows: i) CT, a control diet similar to commercial formulations, containing 20% fishmeal (FM); ii) PP, an experimental diet in which 60% of FM was replaced with hydrolyzed plant proteins; and iii) GG, the PP diet supplemented with 2% *LB-Green_{Grape}*, a fine dry powder consisting of freeze-dried *Albariño* white

Table 1

Ingredients and proximate composition (% dry matter) of experimental diets for juvenile gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*).

Ingredients	Experimental groups		
	CT	PP	GG
Fishmeal LT94 ¹	20.00	8.00	8.00
Lysine ²	1.20	1.20	1.20
Methionine ³	0.50	0.80	0.80
Squid meal ⁴	2.00	2.00	2.00
CPSP90 ⁵	1.00	1.00	1.00
Krill meal ⁶	2.00	2.00	2.00
Wheat gluten ⁷	10.00	12.00	12.00
Soybean protein concentrate ⁸	22.00	29.20	29.20
Pea protein concentrate ⁹	7.50	10.60	10.60
Fish oil ¹⁰	9.00	9.00	9.00
Plant oils ¹¹	4.30	5.70	5.70
Soybean lecithin ¹²	1.00	1.00	1.00
Wheat meal ¹³	16.90	14.40	12.40
Monoammonium phosphate ¹⁴	0.50	1.00	1.00
Vitamin and mineral premix ¹⁵	2.00	2.00	2.00
Vitamin C ¹⁶	0.10	0.10	0.10
<i>LB-Green_{Grape}</i> ¹⁷	–	–	2.00
Proximate composition (% dry matter)			
Crude protein	46.90	46.40	46.60
Crude lipid	18.20	17.90	18.10
Ash	6.90	5.80	5.80
Nfe ¹⁸	22.70	24.10	23.20
Moisture	5.40	5.80	6.30

Dietary codes: CT: control (fishmeal-based) diet; PP: plant-based diet; GG: plant-based diet supplemented with *LB-Green_{Grape}*.¹ 69.4% crude protein, 12.3% crude lipid (Norsildemel, Bergen, Norway).^{2, 3} Lorca Nutrición Animal S.A. (Murcia, Spain).^{4, 5, 6} purchased from Bacarel (UK). CPSP90 is enzymatically pre-digested fishmeal.⁷ 78% crude protein (Lorca Nutrición Animal S.A., Murcia, Spain).⁸ Soycomil, 60% crude protein, 1.5% crude lipid (ADM, Poland).⁹ Pea protein concentrate, 85% crude protein, 1.5% crude lipid (Emilio Peña S.A., Spain).¹⁰ AF117DHA (Afamsa, Spain).¹¹ Blend of soybean, rapeseed, and linseed (4,4,2) oils (Aceites el Niño, Spain).¹² P700IP (Lecico, DE).¹³ Local providers (Almería, Spain).¹⁴ Lorca Nutrición Animal S.A. (Murcia, Spain).¹⁵ *LifeBioencapsulation* S. L. (Almería, Spain). Vitamins (mg kg⁻¹): vitamin A (retinyl acetate), 2,000,000 IU; vitamin D3 (DL-cholecalciferol), 200,000 IU; vitamin E (Lutavit E50), 10,000 mg; vitamin K3 (menadione sodium bisulphite), 2,500 mg; vitamin B1 (thiamine hydrochloride), 3,000 mg; vitamin B2 (riboflavin), 3,000 mg; calcium pantothenate, 10,000 mg; nicotinic acid, 20,000 mg; vitamin B6 (pyridoxine hydrochloride), 2,000 mg; vitamin B9 (folic acid), 1,500 mg; vitamin B12 (cyanocobalamin), 10 mg; vitamin H (biotin), 300 mg; inositol, 50,000 mg; betaine (Betafin S1), 50,000 mg. Minerals (mg kg⁻¹): Co (cobalt carbonate), 65 mg; Cu (cupric sulphate), 900 mg; Fe (iron sulphate), 600 mg; I (potassium iodide), 50 mg; Mn (manganese oxide), 960 mg; Se (sodium selenite), 1 mg; Zn (zinc sulphate), 750 mg; Ca (calcium carbonate), 18.6% (186,000 mg); KCl, 2.41% (24,100 mg); NaCl, 4.0% (40,000 mg).¹⁶ TECNOVIT (Spain).¹⁷ *LB-Green_{Grape}* is a fine dry powder composed by 85% of a freeze-dried extract from *Albariño* white grape marc combined with 15% of a blend of enzymatically hydrolyzed marine and freshwater microalgae (*Arthrospira platensis*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, and *Nannochloropsis gaditana*) containing 37,500 ppm of total polyphenols/kg. This product has been developed within the NeoGiant project (Grant 101036768) by *I-grape* S.L. and *LifeBioencapsulation* S.L., spin-offs from the University of Santiago de Compostela and the University of Almería, respectively.¹⁸ Carbohydrate content estimated by calculation as Nitrogen-free extract = 100 - (% crude protein + % crude lipid + % ash).

grape marc extract combined with a blend of enzymatically hydrolyzed marine and freshwater microalgae (*Arthrospira platensis*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, and *Nannochloropsis gaditana*), with a total polyphenol content of 37,500 ppm. The product was developed within the NeoGiant project (Grant 101036768) by *I-grape* S.L. (Santiago de Compostela, Spain) and *LifeBioencapsulation* S.L. (Almería, Spain), spin-offs from the University of Santiago de Compostela (<https://i-grape.es/producto/extracto-de-uva-blanca-igrabe/>) and the University of Almería (<https://lifebioencapsulation.com>), respectively.

Table 2

Chemical composition (% dry matter) and polyphenol profile (mg kg⁻¹) of the functional ingredient *LB-Green_{Grape}*.

Proximate composition (%)	
Crude protein	11.50 ± 0.90
Crude lipid	2.00 ± 0.70
Total carbohydrates	83.40 ± 1.40
Ash	3.10 ± 0.20
Main polyphenols (mg kg ⁻¹)	
Gallic acid	239.20 ± 15.70
Caftaric acid	15.90 ± 2.10
Procyanidins (B1 + B2 + C1)	1,681.50 ± 51.30
Catechin	1,813.70 ± 88.30
Epicatechin	1,201.30 ± 59.80
Epicatechin gallate	78.40 ± 6.30
Quercetin-3-rutinoside	11.00 ± 2.30
Quercetin-3-glucoside	264.80 ± 12.10
Quercetin-3-glucuronide	283.20 ± 15.20
Quercetin	22.50 ± 3.10
Total phenolic index (mg GAE kg ⁻¹) ¹	35,607.60 ± 534.10

¹ GAE: Gallic Acid Equivalents.

For the enzymatic hydrolysis of plant feedstuffs, ingredients were suspended (100 g dry weight L⁻¹) in 50 mM sodium citrate buffer (pH 5.0) and incubated at 50 °C under continuous agitation for 24 h in the presence of an enzyme blend (xylanase 20,000 U g⁻¹, glucanase 30,000 U g⁻¹, cellulase 10,000 U g⁻¹, and protease 10,000 U g⁻¹), providing an enzyme-to-substrate ratio ([E]/[S]) of 0.05, as described in [Vizcaíno et al. \(2024\)](#). The hydrolysis of microalgal biomass was performed as previously reported by [Galafat et al. \(2022\)](#). All enzymatic pre-treatments were carried out by *LifeBioencapsulation* S.L. (Almería, Spain). The 2% inclusion level of *LB-Green_{Grape}* was selected based on previous trials conducted by our research group in this and other fish species, in which similar nutraceuticals were evaluated within comparable physiological ranges ([Perera et al., 2020](#); [Flores-Moreno et al., 2024](#); [Caderno et al., 2025](#); [Molina-Roque et al., 2025](#)).

Experimental aquafeeds were manufactured by thoroughly mixing all ingredients, including the nutraceutical, followed by the addition of water (up to 300 g kg⁻¹) to obtain a homogeneous dough using a mixer (Sammic BE-40, Sammic, Azpeitia, Spain). The dough was processed using a twin-screw extruder (Evolum 25, Clextral, France) to produce pellets with diameters of 2 and 3 mm. The extruder barrel consisted of four sections, with temperatures set at 90 °C, 92 °C, 95 °C, and 105 °C from inlet to outlet. The resulting pellets were dried at 30 °C for 24 h in a 12 m³ forced-air drying chamber (Airfrio, Almería, Spain) and subsequently cooled to ambient temperature. The following day, vacuum oil coating was applied using a Pegasus PG-10VC LAB vacuum coater (Dinnissen, The Netherlands). Finally, the feeds were stored in sealed plastic bags at -20 °C until use.

The experiment was conducted from September to December 2023 at the indoor facilities of the *Servicios Centrales de Investigación en Cultivos Marinos* (SCI-CM) of the University of Cádiz (CASEM, Puerto Real, Cádiz, Spain; Spanish Operational Code REGA ES11028000312). During a 14-day acclimation period to the experimental facilities, fish were fed a commercial diet (INICIO Plus 805, BioMar). Thereafter, juvenile *S. aurata*, with an initial mean body weight of 13.33 ± 0.16 g, were randomly distributed into nine 400 L tanks, corresponding to an initial stocking density of approximately 1.6 kg m⁻³ (n = 30 fish per tank), with eight water renewals per day. Fish were maintained under stable conditions, with water temperature ranging from 19 °C to 20 °C, oxygen saturation above 85%, salinity of 37 ‰, and a natural photoperiod (10L:14D). The experimental diets were administered to apparent visual satiety six days per week for 84 days. The feeding trial was conducted in a blinded manner, without disclosure of diet composition, to minimize potential bias by personnel. Fish body mass was assessed through biometric sampling every three weeks, while feed intake (FI) was recorded

weekly for each replicate in order to calculate growth performance parameters.

2.3. Sampling procedures

At the end of the experimental feeding period, final sampling was conducted and biometric parameters were recorded. Twelve specimens per experimental diet (four fish per tank, $n = 36$) were randomly selected, deeply anesthetized with a lethal dose of 2-phenoxyethanol (1 mL L⁻¹ seawater), and blood was collected from the caudal vessels using heparinized syringes. Plasma samples were obtained by centrifugation (13,000 × g for 4 min), snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen, and stored at -80 °C until biochemical analysis. Prior to tissue collection, the head was separated from the trunk.

Visceral fat and liver were collected and weighed to calculate the mesenteric somatic index (MSI) and hepatosomatic index (HSI), respectively. Intestinal length was measured to determine the intestinal length index (ILI). For biochemical analyses, samples of skin mucus, liver, and white skeletal muscle were snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 °C. Additionally, representative biopsies of liver, muscle, and head kidney, along with entire hypothalamic lobes and pituitary glands, were collected for gene expression analyses. These tissues were immersed in RNAlater solution (1:10 w/v, Ambion, Applied Biosystems) for 24 h at 4 °C and subsequently stored at -20 °C until total RNA isolation. Furthermore, liver and anterior intestine biopsies were obtained from nine fish per experimental diet (three fish per tank, $n = 27$) for histological examination. Samples were fixed in 10% buffered formalin (pH 7.2) for 48 h.

2.4. Growth performance

The following zootechnical parameters were evaluated: i) Condition factor (K) = $100 \times (\text{body weight}/\text{fork length}^3)$; ii) Feed efficiency (FE) = $\text{weight gain}/\text{total feed intake}$; and iii) Weight gain (WG, %) = $100 \times (\text{body weight increase}/\text{initial body weight})$. Somatic indices were estimated using the following equations: i) Hepatosomatic index (HSI, %) = $100 \times (\text{liver weight}/\text{total body weight})$; ii) Mesenteric index (MSI, %) = $100 \times (\text{perivisceral fat weight}/\text{total body weight})$; and iii) Intestinal length index (ILI, %) = $100 \times (\text{intestine length}/\text{fork length})$. Zootechnical parameters were used to estimate the global feed cost balance for producing one ton of farmed fish, as reported by Flores-Moreno et al. (2024) and Caderno et al. (2025).

2.5. Analysis

2.5.1. Biochemical parameters

Biochemical parameters were measured as previously described by Caderno et al. (2024). Briefly, glucose, lactate, triglyceride (TAG), and cholesterol levels in plasma and skin mucus were quantified using commercial kits (SPINREACT S.A., St. Esteve d'en Bas, Girona, Spain). Total protein concentration was determined using a bicinchoninic acid assay (BCA Protein Assay Kit, Pierce, Rockford, USA). All protocols were adapted to 96-well microplates, and absorbance was measured using a PowerWave 340 microplate spectrophotometer (Bio-Tek Instruments, Winooski, VT, USA) and analyzed with Gen5 v.2.06 software (Gen5™ Data Analysis Software, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA). Glucose and lactate levels in mucus (mg g⁻¹ protein), as well as cortisol levels (ng g⁻¹ protein), were normalized to the protein content measured in this tissue.

The activities of alkaline phosphatase (ALP, EC 3.1.3.1; Kit Ref. 1001131), aspartate aminotransferase (AST, EC 2.6.1.1; Kit Ref. 1001161), and alanine aminotransferase (ALT, EC 2.6.1.2; Kit Ref. 1001171) were determined in plasma using commercial kits from SPINREACT S.A., following the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, enzyme activities were calculated from changes in absorbance at baseline and at 1-min intervals over 3 min, and the mean rate of change ($\Delta A/$

min) was determined. For AST and ALT, enzyme activity was assessed by monitoring the decrease in nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NADH) concentration, whereas for ALP, the formation of p-nitrophenol was measured. In all cases, changes in absorbance were directly proportional to the catalytic activity of the corresponding enzyme. Measurements were performed at an incubation temperature of 37 °C and at wavelengths of 340 nm (AST and ALT) and 405 nm (ALP). All samples were analyzed in duplicate. Enzyme activities were normalized to plasma protein concentration and expressed as mU mg⁻¹ protein.

Liver and muscle biopsies were mechanically homogenized in 7.5 volumes of ice-cold 0.6 N HClO₄ using a blender, neutralized with an equal volume of 1 M KHCO₃, and centrifuged at 3,220 × g for 30 min at 4 °C. The resulting supernatants were collected for tissue metabolite quantification. Prior to centrifugation, an aliquot was taken for TAG determination. Tissue glycogen content was measured following the method of Keppler and Decker (1974), which is based on the enzymatic hydrolysis of glycogen into glucose using amyloglucosidase (Sigma-Aldrich, Ref. A7420). Metabolite levels were determined in duplicate using the commercial kits described above.

2.5.2. Endocrine parameters

Plasma insulin-like growth factor 1 (Igf1) was extracted using an acid-ethanol (1:7) cryoprecipitation method. Plasma Igf1 and Gh levels were determined by competitive inhibition ELISA using commercial kits (CSB-E12122Fh for Igf1 and CSB-E12121Fh for Gh; CUSABIO). Plasma cortisol levels (see Caderno et al., 2024) were quantified using a commercial enzyme immunoassay kit (Cortisol EIA, DETECTX, K003-H, ARBOR ASSAYS, NCal International Standard Kit). All assays were performed according to the manufacturer's instructions.

2.5.3. Total RNA isolation and mRNA expression analysis

The pituitary was homogenized using an Ultra-Turrax® T25 equipped with a dispersing tool S25N-8G (IKA-WERKE, Germany), whereas hypothalamus, head kidney, liver, and muscle tissues were homogenized using a Precellys® Evolution Touch homogenizer (Bertin Technologies, France). Total RNA was extracted from pituitary samples using the NucleoSpin® RNA XS kit (Macherey-Nagel), and from the remaining tissues using the NucleoSpin® RNA kit (Macherey-Nagel). RNA quality was assessed using a 2100 Bioanalyzer (Agilent Technologies), and total RNA concentration was determined using the Qubit™ RNA Broad Range Assay Kit and a Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Only samples with RNA Integrity Numbers (RIN) > 8.0 were used for gene expression analyses. For cDNA synthesis, 50 ng of total RNA from the pituitary and 500 ng from each sample of hypothalamus, head kidney, liver, and muscle were reverse-transcribed in a final volume of 20 μL using the qScript™ cDNA Synthesis Kit (Quanta BioSciences™) on a Mastercycler® proS (Eppendorf AG, Hamburg, Germany). The resulting cDNA was diluted 1:10 in 10 mM Tris and 0.1 mM EDTA (pH 8.0), yielding a final concentration of 2.5 ng μL⁻¹ (250 pg μL⁻¹ for pituitary samples). To optimize quantitative PCR (qPCR) conditions for each gene, a pooled cDNA sample was serially diluted (1:10, ranging from 1 ng to 10 fg for pituitary and from 10 ng to 100 fg for the remaining tissues), and calibration curves were generated. All qPCR assays exhibited R² values > 0.980 and amplification efficiencies between 90.0% and 110.0%. No-template controls (NTC) and no-reverse-transcription controls (NRT) were included to confirm the absence of primer-dimers and genomic DNA contamination, respectively.

qPCR was performed in duplicate using Hard-Shell® white, low-profile, thin-wall 96-well skirted PCR plates sealed with Microseal® B Adhesive Seals (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA). Each reaction contained 0.5 μL of each primer (final concentration: 200 nM), 5 μL of PerfeCTa™ SYBR® Green FastMix™ (Quanta Bio), and 4 μL of diluted cDNA (10 ng, or 1 ng for pituitary samples). Reactions were carried out in a CFX Connect™ Real-Time PCR System (Bio-Rad Laboratories) under the following thermal profile: initial denaturation and enzyme activation at 95 °C for 10 min; 40 cycles of 95 °C for 15 s and 60 °C for 30 s; followed

by a melting curve from 60 °C to 95 °C, increasing by 0.5 °C every 5 s to verify amplicon specificity. Relative gene expression was calculated using the $\Delta\Delta\text{CT}$ method (Livak and Schmittgen, 2001), corrected for amplification efficiency (Pfaffl, 2001), and analyzed using CFX Manager™ software (Bio-Rad). Two reference genes, *actb2* and *efl1a*, were used for normalization, as they exhibited low expression variability in this study and met the GenNorm stability criteria ($\text{CV} < 0.25$ and $\text{M} < 0.5$). The analyzed genes and primer sequences are detailed in Table 3 and Supplementary Material 1.

2.5.4. Histomorphological and histochemical analyses in liver and intestine

Surrounding adipose and connective tissues were carefully removed from the intestinal samples prior to fixation during sampling. Subsequently, liver and anterior intestine samples were washed in running tap water, dehydrated through a graded alcohol series, cleared in xylene, and embedded in paraffin wax. Sections (6 μm) were cut using a rotary microtome and mounted on gelatin-coated slides. The sections were then rehydrated in distilled water and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) following Stevens (1982). The Alcian Blue (AB) staining technique was used to perform specific histochemical reactions for the visualization of carbohydrates and glycoproteins (Martoja and Martoja-Pierson, 1970).

2.5.5. Morphometric analyses in liver and intestine

In liver tissue, hepatocyte area was measured by selecting cells that i) were clearly distinguishable from adjacent hepatocytes and ii) contained a visible nucleus, indicating that a representative portion of the cell had been sectioned. To minimize selection bias, measurements were performed using a systematic serpentine approach, beginning at the upper left corner of each photomicrograph and progressing in a backward “S”-shaped pattern toward the lower right corner. All hepatocytes meeting both criteria were measured until 30 measurements per endpoint were obtained or the end of the slide was reached.

For intestinal morphometry, the highest-quality cross-section of the anterior intestine from each specimen was selected for analysis. The mucosal surface length was divided by the perimeter of the submucosa to calculate the mucosal-to-submucosal surface ratio (MSR). This calculation was based on four diametrically opposed measurements per section (four per fish, totaling 36 measurements per experimental group). Goblet cell density (GC mm^{-2}) was determined by averaging the number of goblet cells counted in four equally spaced, diametrically opposed areas of the same cross-section (four per fish, totaling 36 measurements per experimental group).

For morphometric analyses, micrographs were captured using a light microscope (Nikon Eclipse Ei) equipped with an

MCDXCAM1080P2MPA digital camera. Biometric indices were quantified using Fiji software (ImageJ2, National Institutes of Health, USA).

2.6. Statistics and data processing

All results are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). Data normality and homogeneity of variance were assessed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Levene's tests, respectively. A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed, followed by Tukey's *post hoc* test to determine significant differences among groups. Additionally, correlations between metabolite levels in plasma and skin mucus were evaluated using Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) when normality assumptions were met, and Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (ρ) when they were not. A $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Statistical analyses and figure generation were performed using GraphPad Prism version 8.0 (GraphPad Software, Inc., San Diego, CA, USA; 2018-10-16).

Additional analyses were conducted using RStudio software (version 4.4.0; 2024-04-24). Heatmaps were generated to analyze gene expression profiles in liver and muscle tissues using the ComplexHeatmap (<https://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/ComplexHeatmap.html>) and circlize (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/circlize/index.html>) packages in R. Gene expression values were normalized and converted to Z-scores for comparative analysis. Hierarchical clustering was applied independently to genes and dietary groups using Pearson correlation and average linkage to identify patterns of co-expression and group similarity. Heatmaps employed a diverging color scale to represent upregulated (red) and downregulated (green) genes across dietary treatments. Column annotations indicated dietary groups, facilitating the interpretation of diet-specific expression patterns and overall transcriptional responses in both tissues.

Pearson correlation coefficients and associated *p-values* were calculated to identify relationships among different variables, including molecular markers and endocrine parameters involved in growth and stress regulation. Heatmaps of the correlation matrices were generated using these coefficients, with significance levels indicated as $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**), and $p < 0.001$ (***). The “corrplot” package (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/corrplot/index.html>) was used for visualization. To enhance clarity and interpretability, only the most relevant correlations were included in the main analysis, while the full correlation matrices are provided in the Supplementary Material.

Table 3

Genes included in the qPCR arrays for the hypothalamus (H), pituitary (P), head kidney (HK), liver (L), and muscle (M).

Gene name/category	Symbol	Tissue	Gene name/category	Symbol	Tissue
Reference genes			Somatotropic axis		
Actin beta 2	<i>actb2</i> *	All tissues	Growth hormone	<i>gh</i>	P
Eukaryotic elongation factor 1 alpha	<i>efl1a</i> *	All tissues	Growth hormone-releasing hormone	<i>ghrh</i>	H
Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Interrenal axis			Growth hormone receptor 1	<i>ghr1</i>	P, H, L, M
Corticotropin-releasing hormone	<i>crh</i>	H	Growth hormone receptor 2	<i>ghr2</i>	L, M
Corticotropin-releasing hormone-binding protein	<i>crhbp</i>	H	Insulin-like growth factor 1	<i>igf1</i>	L
Proopiomelanocortin a	<i>pomca</i>	P	Insulin-like growth factor 2b	<i>igf2b</i>	L, M
Proopiomelanocortin b	<i>pomcb</i>	P	Insulin-like growth factor 1a receptor	<i>igf1ra</i>	L, M
Proopiomelanocortin-like	<i>pomcl</i>	P	Insulin-like growth factor 2 receptor	<i>igf2r</i>	L, M
Steroidogenic acute regulatory protein	<i>star</i> *	HK	Insulin-like growth factor binding protein 2a	<i>igfbp2a</i>	L
Cytochrome P450 11B, mitochondrial-like	<i>cyp11b1</i> *	HK	Insulin-like growth factor binding protein 2b	<i>igfbp2b</i>	L
Corticosteroid 11-beta-dehydrogenase isozyme 2-like	<i>hsd11b2</i> *	HK	Insulin-like growth factor binding protein 3	<i>igfbp3</i>	M
Glucocorticoid receptor	<i>nr3c1</i> *	H, P, HK	Insulin-like growth factor binding protein 4	<i>igfbp4</i>	L
Mineralocorticoid receptor	<i>nr3c2</i> *	H, P, HK	Insulin-like growth factor binding protein 5b	<i>igfbp5b</i>	M
			Insulin-like growth factor binding protein 7	<i>igfbp7</i>	L, M
			Insulin receptor a	<i>insra</i>	L
			Insulin receptor b	<i>insrb</i>	L, M
			Somatolactin 1	<i>sl1</i>	P

* Primer sequence obtained from Simó-Mirabet et al. (2025).

Fig. 1. Final mean weight and feed efficiency (FE) of gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) fed experimental diets for 84 days to apparent visual satiety (CT: control diet containing 20% FM; PP: diet with 60% replacement of FM by hydrolyzed plant protein; GG: PP diet supplemented with 2% *LB-GreenGrape*). Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM from triplicate tanks. Different letters indicate statistically significant differences among dietary treatments, as determined by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's *post hoc* test ($p < 0.05$).

3. Results

3.1. Growth performance and somatic indices

No mortality was recorded throughout the experimental period. Fig. 1 and Table 4 present the results for growth parameters and somatic indices. Fish fed the CT diet showed higher final length, final weight, FE, and FI, whereas those fed the PP diet exhibited the lowest values ($p < 0.05$). The inclusion of the nutraceutical resulted in a partial recovery of these parameters. Weight gain was significantly higher only in fish fed the CT diet ($p < 0.05$). A decrease in ILI was observed in fish fed the plant-based diet (PP), but not in those receiving the same diet supplemented with the nutraceutical (GG; $p < 0.05$). No significant differences were observed among the experimental groups for the remaining parameters (K, HSI, and MSI; $p > 0.05$).

3.2. Biochemical parameters

Table 5 presents the biochemical parameters analyzed in plasma, skin mucus, liver, and muscle. No significant differences were observed in plasma levels of glucose, lactate, protein, cholesterol, or cortisol, nor in the activities of ALP, AST, and ALT ($p > 0.05$). However, plasma TAG

Table 4

Growth performance and somatic indices of gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) fed experimental diets for 84 days to apparent visual satiety (CT: control diet containing 20% FM; PP: diet with 60% replacement of FM by hydrolyzed plant protein; GG: PP diet supplemented with 2% *LB-GreenGrape*). Feed intake and growth parameters are expressed as mean \pm SEM from triplicate tanks. Somatic indices are expressed as mean \pm SEM from 12 fish per experimental group. Different superscript letters within the same row indicate statistically significant differences among dietary treatments, as determined by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's *post hoc* test ($p < 0.05$). Significant *p-values* are shown in bold.

Parameters	Experimental groups			<i>p-value</i>
	CT	PP	GG	
Final length (cm)	14.04 \pm 0.20 ^a	13.32 \pm 0.22 ^b	13.74 \pm 0.19 ^{ab}	0.048
K	1.94 \pm 0.03	1.94 \pm 0.04	1.94 \pm 0.03	0.994
FI (g DM/fish/day)	0.63 \pm 0.03 ^a	0.55 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.61 \pm 0.01 ^{ab}	0.047
WG (%)	281.00 \pm 4.71 ^a	233.50 \pm 5.37 ^b	244.90 \pm 4.89 ^b	<0.001
HSI (%)	2.08 \pm 0.11	1.92 \pm 0.12	1.81 \pm 0.13	0.277
MSI (%)	0.96 \pm 0.10	1.03 \pm 0.22	0.94 \pm 0.18	0.923
ILI (%)	107.50 \pm 4.78 ^a	87.27 \pm 3.63 ^b	108.10 \pm 8.27 ^a	0.043

Abbreviations: DM: Dry matter; FI: Feed intake; HSI: Hepatosomatic index; ILI: Intestinal length index; K: Condition factor; MSI: Mesenteric index; WG: Weight gain.

levels were significantly higher in GG-fed fish and lowest in CT-fed fish ($p < 0.05$). In skin mucus, a significant increase in lactate levels was detected in the GG group, whereas lower values were observed in the PP group ($p < 0.05$). The remaining metabolites in mucus, as well as cortisol levels, showed no significant differences among groups ($p > 0.05$). At the hepatic level, no significant differences were observed among dietary treatments ($p > 0.05$). In muscle, a significant decrease in glycogen concentrations was detected in fish from the GG group compared to the CT group ($p < 0.05$). Muscle TAG levels were significantly reduced in the PP group compared to CT and showed partial recovery in fish fed the GG diet ($p < 0.05$). No significant differences were observed in muscle glucose and lactate levels ($p > 0.05$).

Plasma levels of hormones involved in the growth axis, namely Gh and Igf1, as well as the Igf1/Gh ratio, were influenced by diet composition (Fig. 2). Gh levels were higher in fish fed the PP diet, lowest in the CT group, and partially restored in the GG group ($p < 0.05$; Fig. 2A). In contrast, Igf1 levels showed an inverse pattern, with increased levels in the GG group compared to both CT and PP groups ($p < 0.05$; Fig. 2B). Accordingly, the Igf1/Gh ratio increased in the nutraceutical-supplemented group (GG) and decreased in the PP group compared to CT ($p < 0.05$; Fig. 2C).

Regarding correlations between plasma and skin mucus biochemical parameters, significant relationships were found for cortisol ($\rho = 0.5444$, $p = 0.009$; Fig. 3A) and glucose ($r = 0.5162$, $p = 0.004$; Fig. 3B) when considering all samples irrespective of dietary treatment. In contrast, lactate and protein levels were not significantly correlated between the two matrices ($p > 0.05$; Fig. 3D and E, respectively). When analyzed by diet, a significant correlation between plasma and mucus glucose levels was observed only in the PP group ($r = 0.5888$, $p = 0.044$; Fig. 3C). Additional results regarding correlations between plasma and skin mucus parameters for each dietary treatment are presented in Supplementary Material 2.

3.3. Molecular markers

3.3.1. Somatotrophic axis

Regarding genes involved in growth-related processes (Table 6), no significant differences in expression were observed at the hypothalamic level ($p > 0.05$). In the pituitary gland, *gh* expression was significantly higher in the GG group compared to the control (CT) group ($p < 0.05$), whereas expression levels of *ghr1* and *sl1* did not differ significantly ($p > 0.05$). In the liver, a significant downregulation of *ghr1* and *igf2b* expression was observed in fish fed the GG diet, with higher expression levels detected in the CT group ($p < 0.05$). Expression of *igf1* was also significantly higher in the CT group compared to both PP and GG groups ($p < 0.05$). Conversely, *igfbp7* expression was significantly upregulated in the GG group and reduced in the PP group ($p < 0.05$). In muscle, *ghr2* expression was significantly lower in the CT group compared to both plant-based diet groups (PP and GG; $p < 0.05$), whereas *igf2r* expression

Table 5

Biochemical parameters in plasma, skin mucus, liver, and muscle of juvenile gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) fed experimental diets for 84 days to apparent visual satiety (CT, PP, and GG). Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM from 12 fish per experimental group. Additional methodological and statistical details are provided in Table 4.

Parameters	Experimental groups			p-value
	CT	PP	GG	
PLASMA				
Glucose (mM)	4.33 \pm 0.15	4.06 \pm 0.17	3.99 \pm 0.10	0.207
Lactate (mM)	0.66 \pm 0.06	0.60 \pm 0.07	0.65 \pm 0.04	0.704
Triglycerides (mM)	1.62 \pm 0.21 ^b	2.22 \pm 0.32 ^{ab}	2.70 \pm 0.27 ^a	0.028
Proteins (mg mL ⁻¹)	35.91 \pm 1.06	35.57 \pm 1.02	34.40 \pm 0.81	0.516
Cholesterol (mg dL ⁻¹)	156.10 \pm 8.59	156.10 \pm 8.94	151.60 \pm 7.14	0.908
Cortisol (ng mL ⁻¹)	10.96 \pm 5.68	12.13 \pm 4.10	11.11 \pm 5.76	0.983
ALP (mU mg ⁻¹ protein)	3.45 \pm 0.25	3.29 \pm 0.08	3.58 \pm 0.18	0.565
AST (mU mg ⁻¹ protein)	1.02 \pm 0.27	0.92 \pm 0.21	0.73 \pm 0.16	0.641
ALT (mU mg ⁻¹ protein)	0.10 \pm 0.02	0.12 \pm 0.03	0.13 \pm 0.03	0.684
SKIN MUCUS				
Glucose (mg g ⁻¹ protein)	31.49 \pm 4.99	33.94 \pm 5.96	38.21 \pm 4.66	0.659
Lactate (mg g ⁻¹ protein)	4.34 \pm 0.34 ^{ab}	3.63 \pm 0.34 ^b	6.08 \pm 0.72 ^a	0.005
Proteins (mg mL ⁻¹)	4.69 \pm 1.16	4.44 \pm 0.90	3.62 \pm 0.73	0.707
Cortisol (ng g ⁻¹ protein)	129.80 \pm 28.63	144.40 \pm 39.80	107.30 \pm 34.09	0.752
LIVER				
Glucose (mg g ⁻¹ ww)	1.99 \pm 0.12	1.84 \pm 0.13	1.76 \pm 0.11	0.426
Glycogen (mg g ⁻¹ ww)	18.20 \pm 0.82	16.78 \pm 0.54	16.28 \pm 0.56	0.110
Lactate (mg g ⁻¹ ww)	0.07 \pm 0.01	0.08 \pm 0.01	0.09 \pm 0.01	0.301
Triglycerides (mg g ⁻¹ ww)	50.77 \pm 5.19	52.74 \pm 3.61	58.18 \pm 2.07	0.379
MUSCLE				
Glucose (mg g ⁻¹ ww)	0.23 \pm 0.01	0.22 \pm 0.02	0.20 \pm 0.01	0.380
Glycogen (mg g ⁻¹ ww)	0.09 \pm 0.02 ^a	0.07 \pm 0.01 ^{ab}	0.04 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.038
Lactate (mg g ⁻¹ ww)	3.86 \pm 0.18	4.00 \pm 0.23	3.91 \pm 0.14	0.862
Triglycerides (mg g ⁻¹ ww)	16.38 \pm 1.25 ^a	11.85 \pm 1.40 ^b	13.38 \pm 1.15 ^{ab}	0.044

Abbreviations: ALP: Alkaline phosphatase; ALT: Alanine aminotransferase; AST: Aspartate aminotransferase; ww: wet weight.

was significantly higher only in the PP group ($p < 0.05$). No significant differences were detected in the expression of the remaining genes analyzed in liver and muscle ($p > 0.05$).

To further explore potential diet-related patterns not captured by univariate analyses, multivariate approaches were applied to the gene expression dataset, allowing the integration of molecular outcomes. Heatmaps (Fig. 4) provide a refined representation of co-expression patterns among genes related to the somatotrophic axis in liver and muscle tissues, revealing clear diet-dependent clustering. In the liver (Fig. 4A), the GG diet formed the most distinct cluster, whereas PP and CT exhibited more similar co-expression profiles. Fish fed the CT diet showed a general trend toward upregulation of most hepatic genes, whereas those in the PP group tended toward downregulation. Notably, *ghr1*, *igf1*, *igf2b*, and *igfbp4* were markedly upregulated in the CT group but tended to be downregulated in both plant-based diets, particularly in GG. Conversely, the GG diet showed upregulation of *ghr2*, *igfbp2a*, *igfbp2b*, and *igfbp7*, which were downregulated in the PP group. In muscle (Fig. 4B), fish fed plant-based diets (PP and GG) exhibited similar co-expression patterns, whereas the CT group formed a distinct cluster characterized by a general downregulation of most analyzed genes. Specifically, *igf2b*, *igf2r*, and *igfbp5b* were upregulated in the PP group, while *insrb*, *ghr2*, *igf1ra*, and *igfbp3* were upregulated in the GG group.

The correlation matrix (Fig. 5) highlighted associations among growth-related gene expression, plasma Gh and Igf1 levels, and final mean body weight, providing insight into coordinated responses across physiological levels. In fish fed the CT diet (Fig. 5A), positive and significant correlations were observed among hepatic *ghr1*, *igf1*, and *igf2b*. Additionally, *igf2b* expression was positively correlated with hepatic *ghr2* expression and with plasma Gh levels. Plasma Igf1 levels were negatively correlated with both plasma Gh levels and hepatic *ghr1* and *igf2b* expression. In the pituitary gland, *gh* expression was negatively correlated with *sl1*. Under the PP diet (Fig. 5B), plasma Igf1 levels were

negatively correlated with pituitary *sl1* expression. Hepatic *igf1* and *ghr1* expression were positively correlated. At the pituitary level, *ghr1* expression showed a positive correlation with hypothalamic *ghrh* and hepatic *igfbp7*, and a negative correlation with pituitary *gh* expression. In the GG diet group (Fig. 5C), plasma Igf1 levels were negatively correlated with hepatic *ghr2* and *igfbp2b* expression. Pituitary *sl1* expression was negatively correlated with both pituitary *ghr1* expression and plasma Igf1 levels. Hepatic *igf1* expression showed positive correlations with both final body weight and plasma Gh levels. Moreover, final body weight was also positively correlated with hepatic *igfbp2b* expression. Additional correlation patterns observed under CT, PP, and GG diets are provided in Supplementary Materials 3, 4, and 5, respectively.

3.3.2. Stress axis

No significant differences were observed in the expression of the analyzed stress-related genes at the hypothalamic and pituitary levels ($p > 0.05$; Table 7). Similarly, the relative expression of *cyp11b1* and *nr3c2* in the head kidney did not differ significantly ($p > 0.05$). Expression of *star* was significantly higher in CT-fed fish and lower in the GG group ($p < 0.05$). In contrast, *hsd11b2* and *nr3c1* expression levels were significantly increased in the PP group compared to the control group, with intermediate values observed in fish fed the GG diet ($p < 0.05$).

Correlation matrices revealed diet-specific associations in the expression of stress-related genes along the HPI axis (Fig. 6). Under the CT diet (Fig. 6A), significant positive correlations were detected among pituitary *pomca*, *pomcb*, and *pomcl*. In the head kidney, *star* expression was positively correlated with *cyp11b1*. At the hypothalamic level, *crh* expression was positively correlated with *crhbp* expression. In the PP diet group (Fig. 6B), a similar correlation pattern was observed; however, pituitary *pomcl* expression did not show significant correlations with *pomca* or *pomcb*. Under the GG diet (Fig. 6C), correlation patterns were broadly consistent with those observed in the CT group, although

Fig. 2. Plasma endocrine parameters of gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) fed experimental diets for 84 days to apparent visual satiety (CT, PP, and GG): (A) growth hormone (Gh, ng mL⁻¹); (B) insulin-like growth factor 1 (Igf1, ng mL⁻¹); (C) Igf1/Gh ratio. Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM from 12 fish per experimental group. Additional methodological and statistical details are provided in Fig. 1.

Fig. 3. Correlations of metabolic and endocrine variables between plasma and skin mucus of gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) fed experimental diets for 84 days to apparent visual satiety (CT, PP, and GG): (A) cortisol; (B) glucose; (C) glucose (PP diet); (D) lactate; (E) protein. Symbols: r , Pearson correlation; ρ , Spearman correlation ($p < 0.05$). Values are expressed in the same units as in Table 5. Additional methodological and statistical details are provided in Fig. 1. Significant p -values are shown in bold.

some differences were detected. At the hypothalamic level, *crh* and *crhbp* expression did not show significant correlations. Notably, in this group, head kidney *star* and *cyp11b1* expression were negatively correlated with pituitary *pomca* and *pomcb* expression. Additional correlation patterns observed under CT, PP, and GG diets are provided in Supplementary Materials 6, 7, and 8, respectively.

3.4. Morphometric analyses in liver and intestine

In the liver, hepatocyte area was significantly greater in fish from the PP group compared to those from the CT and GG groups ($p < 0.05$; Fig. 7A). In the anterior intestine, the MSR did not differ significantly among groups ($p > 0.05$; Fig. 7B). GC density was significantly higher in

the GG group compared to both PP and CT dietary treatments ($p < 0.05$; Fig. 7C).

3.5. Feed cost analysis

The overall feed cost balance is presented in Table 8. Fish fed the PP and GG diets required a greater amount of feed to produce one ton of biomass compared to those fed the control diet (CT). Supplementation of the plant protein-based diet with *LB-GreenGrape* improved FE and reduced feed requirements. This improvement was reflected in the total cost balance. Although both PP and GG diets remained more expensive than the CT diet, the inclusion of *LB-GreenGrape* resulted in a net feed cost reduction of approximately €61 per ton of fish biomass produced

Table 6

Relative gene expression ($\Delta\Delta\text{CT}$) of genes involved in the growth axis of gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) fed experimental diets for 84 days to apparent visual satiety (CT, PP, and GG). Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM ($n = 8\text{--}11$ for muscle and $n = 12$ for other tissues). Additional methodological and statistical details are provided in Table 4.

Genes	Experimental groups			<i>p</i> -value
	CT	PP	GG	
HYPOTHALAMUS				
<i>ghrh</i>	1.07 \pm 0.06	1.14 \pm 0.15	1.09 \pm 0.07	0.891
<i>ghr1</i>	1.00 \pm 0.04	0.91 \pm 0.03	0.91 \pm 0.04	0.196
PITUITARY				
<i>gh</i>	0.74 \pm 0.11 ^b	0.83 \pm 0.08 ^{ab}	1.07 \pm 0.06 ^a	0.043
<i>ghr1</i>	0.80 \pm 0.09	0.69 \pm 0.05	0.71 \pm 0.07	0.535
<i>sl1</i>	0.83 \pm 0.14	0.62 \pm 0.06	0.64 \pm 0.09	0.299
LIVER				
<i>ghr1</i>	1.45 \pm 0.22 ^a	1.01 \pm 0.14 ^{ab}	0.68 \pm 0.08 ^b	0.005
<i>ghr2</i>	0.92 \pm 0.10	0.92 \pm 0.09	0.99 \pm 0.08	0.805
<i>igf1</i>	1.53 \pm 0.11 ^a	1.17 \pm 0.10 ^b	1.09 \pm 0.03 ^b	0.005
<i>igf2b</i>	1.22 \pm 0.18 ^a	0.90 \pm 0.10 ^{ab}	0.71 \pm 0.06 ^b	0.017
<i>igf1ra</i>	1.19 \pm 0.12	1.44 \pm 0.12	1.44 \pm 0.07	0.175
<i>igf2r</i>	1.07 \pm 0.09	1.20 \pm 0.07	1.19 \pm 0.11	0.529
<i>igfbp2a</i>	0.97 \pm 0.09	0.92 \pm 0.07	1.01 \pm 0.06	0.662
<i>igfbp2b</i>	1.13 \pm 0.05	1.00 \pm 0.05	1.13 \pm 0.07	0.176
<i>igfbp4</i>	1.07 \pm 0.13	0.95 \pm 0.09	0.90 \pm 0.06	0.472
<i>igfbp7</i>	0.81 \pm 0.06 ^{ab}	0.70 \pm 0.05 ^b	0.92 \pm 0.05 ^a	0.022
<i>insra</i>	0.98 \pm 0.07	0.90 \pm 0.05	0.93 \pm 0.06	0.659
<i>insrb</i>	1.26 \pm 0.10	1.38 \pm 0.08	1.29 \pm 0.06	0.536
MUSCLE				
<i>ghr1</i>	1.46 \pm 0.14	1.41 \pm 0.28	1.40 \pm 0.12	0.971
<i>ghr2</i>	0.55 \pm 0.10 ^b	1.30 \pm 0.27 ^a	1.35 \pm 0.19 ^a	0.006
<i>igf2b</i>	1.04 \pm 0.07	1.21 \pm 0.12	1.16 \pm 0.10	0.508
<i>igf1ra</i>	1.06 \pm 0.11	1.26 \pm 0.11	1.32 \pm 0.15	0.374
<i>igf2r</i>	1.07 \pm 0.11 ^b	1.62 \pm 0.24 ^a	1.07 \pm 0.08 ^b	0.018
<i>igfbp3</i>	0.98 \pm 0.11	1.26 \pm 0.14	1.39 \pm 0.21	0.236
<i>igfbp5b</i>	0.90 \pm 0.07	1.08 \pm 0.13	0.95 \pm 0.10	0.372
<i>igfbp7</i>	1.20 \pm 0.19	1.12 \pm 0.17	1.11 \pm 0.09	0.890
<i>insrb</i>	1.19 \pm 0.16	1.30 \pm 0.16	1.41 \pm 0.16	0.616

compared to the unsupplemented plant-based diet (PP).

4. Discussion

The dietary strategy evaluated in this study for *S. aurata* provides a sustainable and cost-efficient alternative by combining biotechnologically treated plant proteins with a functional ingredient based on hydrolyzed microalgae and grape marc extract. This approach reduces dependence on marine-derived ingredients, such as FM and fish oil (FO), while valorizing biomass that would otherwise be discarded. In this context, the combination of enzymatic treatment of plant proteins with the inclusion of *LB-GreenGrape* enhances digestibility and nutrient bioavailability (Molina-Roque et al., 2025), resulting in improved growth performance and FE in the supplemented diet, with values approaching those of the control group (CT). Consequently, a reduction in feed usage and overall feed costs was observed in the GG group compared to the unsupplemented plant-based diet, with estimated savings of approximately €61 per ton of fish produced. These findings are consistent with previous studies reporting the beneficial effects of microalgae-based functional ingredients, both in diets simulating commercial formulations (Perera et al., 2020; Flores-Moreno et al., 2024) and in those containing high levels of plant protein without biotechnological processing (Caderno et al., 2025). Collectively, this evidence supports the potential of such compounds to improve FE and reduce production costs, thereby contributing to more sustainable and circular aquafeed formulations.

4.1. Growth axis

The economic profitability of aquafeeds is closely linked to fish growth performance. Although the PP diet was enzymatically hydrolyzed to enhance digestibility and reduce ANF, growth performance remained suboptimal. This outcome may be attributed to a nutritional imbalance that was not fully corrected despite the substantial modification of the feed formulation and nutrient profile of the experimental diets. Fish fed the PP diet exhibited reduced body length, final weight, FE, and WG compared to the other groups.

In this context, a broader analysis of the Gh/Igf axis and related gene expression provides insight into the underlying mechanisms, which are likely associated with nutritional status (Picha et al., 2008). In *S. aurata*, circulating Gh and Igf1 levels are considered key biomarkers of both growth performance and nutritional status (Pérez-Sánchez et al., 2018). The condition known as Gh resistance or insensitivity, characterized by elevated Gh levels, reduced Igf1 levels, and diminished hepatic responsiveness to the anabolic effects of Gh, has been associated with catabolic states and metabolic imbalance (Pérez-Sánchez and Le Bail, 1999). This pattern was clearly observed in the present study in fish fed the plant protein-rich diet (PP) and represents a phenomenon widely documented in gilthead seabream (Pérez-Sánchez et al., 1995; Gómez-Requeni et al., 2003, 2004; Benedito-Palos et al., 2007; Saera-Vila et al., 2009), as well as in other fish species (Deng et al., 2004; Fox et al., 2006; Men et al., 2014; Tu et al., 2015; Hassaan et al., 2019) subjected to plant-based diets, fasting, protein deficiency, or other conditions that impair metabolic homeostasis.

Thus, the elevated plasma Gh levels observed in the PP group may reflect a compensatory response aimed at mitigating impaired growth, likely resulting from multiple factors: i) hepatic resistance to Gh due to altered expression of its hepatic receptors; ii) reduced Gh sensitivity in peripheral tissues, as indicated by the downregulation of *igf1* and *igf2b*; iii) low circulating Igf1 levels, which may prevent activation of the classical long-loop negative feedback on pituitary *gh* transcription; iv) activation of alternative feedback mechanisms along the somatotrophic axis, such as the negative correlations between plasma Igf1 and pituitary *sl1* expression, and between pituitary *gh* and *ghr1* expression; and v) a trend toward increased hypothalamic *ghrh* expression in the PP group (although not statistically significant), which may represent a compensatory response to reduced Gh/Igf1 axis activity. This is further supported by the positive correlation between *ghrh* and pituitary *ghr1* expression, which may be associated with Gh signaling (Duan, 1998; Gómez-Requeni et al., 2003; Deng et al., 2004; Fox et al., 2006; Wong et al., 2006; Picha et al., 2008; Saera-Vila et al., 2009; Sánchez-Moya et al., 2023).

This imbalance results in a low Igf1/Gh ratio and impaired growth, highlighting a decoupling between hormonal signaling and tissue responsiveness. Consequently, lipid reserve mobilization is promoted (Gómez-Requeni et al., 2004; Tu et al., 2015; Khieokhajonkhet et al., 2016; Bertucci et al., 2019). The observed reduction in muscle TAG in the PP group supports this interpretation, suggesting enhanced lipid oxidation as an energy source under a catabolic hormonal profile (characterized by elevated Gh and reduced Igf1), which disrupts the somatotrophic axis. This Gh resistance may represent an adaptive response to nutritional stress, prioritizing energy mobilization over somatic growth (Pérez-Sánchez and Le Bail, 1999; Company et al., 2001; Pérez-Sánchez et al., 2018).

However, the suboptimal growth response observed in the PP group may be partially attributed to reduced FI, a factor previously identified as critical in similar studies (Gómez-Requeni et al., 2004; Benedito-Palos et al., 2007; Hevrøy et al., 2008; Men et al., 2014). This reduction is likely associated with the lower palatability of plant-based diets (Picha et al., 2008; Caderno et al., 2025), as well as alterations in gastrointestinal hormone regulation, including changes in the dynamics and spatio-temporal distribution of cholecystokinin and ghrelin (Caderno et al., 2026). In general, increased FI stimulates the Gh/Igf axis and enhances

Fig. 4. Heatmaps showing expression profiles of growth-related genes in gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) fed experimental diets for 84 days to apparent visual satiety (CT: control diet containing 20% FM; PP: diet with 60% replacement of FM by hydrolyzed plant protein; GG: PP diet supplemented with 2% *LB-Green_{Grape}*): (A) liver; (B) muscle. Data are expressed as Z-scores (calculated across all samples and averaged per experimental group), where red indicates higher and green lower values relative to the mean expression of each gene. Hierarchical clustering was applied to both genes and dietary groups using Pearson correlation and average linkage. For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.

somatic growth, in contrast to the suppressive effects of fasting or nutritional deficiency (Bertucci et al., 2019). In the present study, fish fed the CT and GG diets exhibited higher FI, supporting a more effective activation of the somatotrophic axis. In the control group (CT), reduced pituitary *gh* expression and circulating Gh levels were sufficient to induce hepatic *ghr1* expression, enhance Gh sensitivity, and stimulate *igf1* and *igf2b* production (both positively correlated and upregulated), thereby promoting adequate growth.

The inclusion of *LB-Green_{Grape}* in the plant protein-based diet enabled a partial recovery of several growth parameters and associated transcriptional responses. Nevertheless, hepatic expression of *ghr1*, *igf1*, and *igf2b* was lowest in the GG group, suggesting reduced Gh sensitivity (Uchida et al., 2003; Pérez-Sánchez et al., 2018). This expression profile is typically associated with decreased plasma Igf1 levels, and potentially Igf2 (although less extensively studied), which can impair growth under stress or nutritional challenges (Fox et al., 2006; Saera-Vila et al., 2009; Bertucci et al., 2019). Paradoxically, fish in the GG group exhibited the highest plasma Igf1 concentrations and an elevated Igf1/Gh ratio, suggesting the activation of compensatory mechanisms that sustain

somatotropic signaling beyond the classical Gh/Igf1 axis. This likely contributed to improved growth performance, as supported by the positive correlation between body weight and hepatic *igf1* expression. Notably, the long-loop negative feedback mechanism, typically induced by elevated Igf1 levels on pituitary *gh* transcription (Wong et al., 2006), was not observed, as pituitary *gh* expression was higher in this group. This finding may support the proposed autocrine/paracrine role of intrapituitary Igf1 in modulating somatotroph cell activity (Eppler et al., 2007; Shved et al., 2011), although *igf1* expression in the pituitary was not assessed in the present study.

The elevated plasma Igf1 levels in the GG group, together with improved growth, likely result from multiple interacting factors. These may include sustained Igf1 signaling in peripheral tissues, supported by higher (although not statistically significant) *igf1ra* expression in liver and muscle (see heatmap), suggesting continued pathway activity without activation of the typical negative feedback mechanisms that reduce tissue sensitivity under conditions of Igf1 excess (Sánchez-Moya et al., 2023). Furthermore, the negative correlations observed between pituitary *sl1* expression and both pituitary *ghr1* expression and plasma

Fig. 5. Pearson correlation matrices showing relationships among growth-related parameters, including final mean body weight, plasma Gh and Igf1 levels, and gene expression along the Gh/Ghr/Igf1 axis in gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) fed experimental diets for 84 days to apparent visual satiety (CT: control diet containing 20% FM; PP: diet with 60% replacement of FM by hydrolyzed plant protein; GG: PP diet supplemented with 2% *LB-Green_{Grape}*): (A) CT; (B) PP; (C) GG. Tissue abbreviations: H: Hypothalamus; P: Pituitary; L: Liver. Asterisks indicate statistically significant correlations: $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**), and $p < 0.001$ (***)

Igf1 levels suggest that activity of the somatotrophic axis in the GG group reduces the requirement for increased *sl1* expression. Given the role of somatolactin in energy metabolism (Company et al., 2001; de Celis et al., 2004), its downregulation (not statistically significant) is consistent with increased sensitivity and efficiency of the Gh/Igf1 axis under this dietary condition. Unlike Gh, Igfs are not stored, and their bioavailability is regulated by Igf-binding proteins (Igfbps) (Pérez-Sánchez et al., 2018). In GG-fed fish, the hepatic upregulation of these proteins (clustered in the heatmap and showing increased expression in this group), particularly *igfbp7*, may partly explain the elevated Igf1 levels and improved growth. This interpretation is further supported by the positive correlation between body weight and *igfbp2b* expression. These effects occur despite reduced hepatic Gh signaling (García de la Serrana and Macqueen, 2018), as indicated by the lower expression of hepatic *ghr1* and the negative correlation between Igf1 and *ghr2*. However, the roles of Igfbps vary depending on species and physiological context (Sánchez-Moya et al., 2023), and the specific function of *igfbp7* remains unclear. These effects may be modulated by *LB-Green_{Grape}*, whose bioactive compounds could influence Igf1 stability or secretion, potentially through mechanisms partially independent of classical Gh signaling pathways. In line with this hypothesis, previous studies supplementing plant-based diets with functional additives (Rolland et al.,

2015; Benedito-Palos et al., 2016; Hassaan et al., 2019), microalgae (Reis et al., 2021), or grape extracts (Yang et al., 2023) have reported positive transcriptional effects on the somatotrophic axis.

At the muscle level, gene expression changes under plant-based diets remain poorly understood (Dhanasiri et al., 2020). Although most genes did not show statistically significant differences, a more detailed analysis revealed a general trend toward increased expression in both plant-based diet groups (see heatmap). Notably, *ghr2* expression was elevated in the PP group, mirroring plasma Gh levels and suggesting its involvement in stress-related signaling and energy mobilization. This response is likely linked to enhanced lipolysis and a catabolic state (Saera-Vila et al., 2005; Sissener et al., 2013; Gómez-Requeni et al., 2019; Perelló-Amorós et al., 2021; Sánchez-Moya et al., 2023), which may be associated with the observed depletion of intramuscular TAG in this group. Interestingly, muscle *ghr2* expression was also elevated in the GG group, in which a significant depletion of muscle glycogen was detected, although the underlying mechanisms require further investigation. Additionally, TAG levels were elevated in GG-fed fish across various tissues, although not always significantly, and, unlike in the PP group, muscle TAG levels showed partial recovery. These findings are consistent with those reported by Benedito-Palos et al. (2007), who described local *igf2* and *ghr2* responses in fish fed vegetable oils. In

Table 7

Relative gene expression ($\Delta\Delta CT$) of genes involved in the stress response of gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) fed experimental diets for 84 days to apparent visual satiety (CT, PP, and GG). Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM from 12 fish per experimental group. Additional methodological and statistical details are provided in Table 4.

Genes	Experimental groups			<i>p</i> -value
	CT	PP	GG	
HYPOTHALAMUS				
<i>crh</i>	1.00 \pm 0.04	1.07 \pm 0.05	0.97 \pm 0.03	0.299
<i>crhbp</i>	1.21 \pm 0.13	1.15 \pm 0.23	1.20 \pm 0.21	0.982
<i>nr3c1</i>	0.77 \pm 0.04	0.69 \pm 0.06	0.83 \pm 0.04	0.134
<i>nr3c2</i>	1.19 \pm 0.06	1.03 \pm 0.05	1.16 \pm 0.09	0.266
PITUITARY				
<i>pomca</i>	1.00 \pm 0.12	0.90 \pm 0.06	0.95 \pm 0.10	0.752
<i>pomcb</i>	0.79 \pm 0.06	0.83 \pm 0.08	0.84 \pm 0.08	0.940
<i>pomcl</i>	0.83 \pm 0.14	0.62 \pm 0.06	0.64 \pm 0.09	0.299
<i>nr3c1</i>	0.85 \pm 0.07	0.80 \pm 0.04	0.78 \pm 0.05	0.653
<i>nr3c2</i>	1.15 \pm 0.10	1.28 \pm 0.08	1.23 \pm 0.09	0.606
HEAD KIDNEY				
<i>star</i>	1.46 \pm 0.24 ^a	1.37 \pm 0.30 ^{ab}	0.57 \pm 0.13 ^b	0.028
<i>cyp11b1</i>	1.51 \pm 0.22	1.08 \pm 0.22	0.97 \pm 0.22	0.218
<i>hsd11b2</i>	0.74 \pm 0.04 ^b	0.96 \pm 0.06 ^a	0.89 \pm 0.08 ^{ab}	0.043
<i>nr3c1</i>	0.85 \pm 0.04 ^b	1.00 \pm 0.05 ^a	0.94 \pm 0.03 ^{ab}	0.043
<i>nr3c2</i>	1.24 \pm 0.10	1.09 \pm 0.08	1.05 \pm 0.09	0.297

agreement with this, the muscle heatmap revealed similar co-expression patterns among *igf2b*, its receptor (*igf2r*), and *igfbp5b*, which clustered together. However, *igf2r* was downregulated in CT and GG diets and showed higher expression in the muscle of the PP group, diverging from hepatic *igf2b* expression patterns. Overall, these results highlight that gene duplicates may play tissue-specific roles in compensatory muscle growth (Pérez-Sánchez et al., 2018), reinforcing the importance of extrahepatic regulation under conditions of nutritional stress.

4.2. Stress axis and metabolic response

The hypothalamus-pituitary-interrenal axis (HPI), primarily through cortisol, regulates stress responses and modulates key physiological processes (Ellis et al., 2012; Tsalaouta et al., 2018). In the present study, cortisol levels in both plasma and skin mucus remained stable across the three experimental diets. While mucus cortisol is widely recognized as a non-invasive marker of acute stress, other tissues, such as scales, may provide more reliable indicators of chronic stress, including that induced by nutritional imbalance (Carbajal et al., 2019). Significant positive correlations between glucose and cortisol were observed when considering all experimental diets collectively; whereas a significant plasma-mucus glucose correlation was detected only in the PP group. This finding supports the notion that the glucose-to-protein ratio is one of the most sensitive markers in skin mucus (Fernández-Alacid et al., 2018). Lactate, which is rapidly oxidized under stress conditions (Omlin and Weber, 2010), may have limited availability for excretion into mucus. In this study, despite no correlation between plasma and mucus lactate levels, the PP group exhibited significantly lower mucus lactate levels, with trends toward lower plasma levels and higher muscle concentrations. This pattern may indicate localized retention or utilization of lactate as an adaptive response to low-grade nutritional stress, thereby limiting its transfer to mucus (Fernández-Alacid et al., 2019). These results suggest that, under mild nutritional stress and in the absence of marked cortisol elevation, skin mucus may have limited utility in reflecting systemic metabolic markers.

Nutritional stress derived from unbalanced formulations, particularly those rich in plant protein, can impair endocrine function, growth, immunity, and gut integrity in fish (Desai et al., 2012; Caderno et al.,

2025; Molina-Roque et al., 2025). However, their impact across different levels of the HPI axis has been less extensively studied, particularly at the molecular level, highlighting the need for deeper insight into diet-stress interactions. In the present study, no significant changes were observed in the expression of stress-related genes in the hypothalamus or pituitary. Notably, a positive correlation between *crh* and *crhbp* expression suggests functional co-regulation under control conditions (CT) and in the PP group. In contrast, this relationship was disrupted in the GG group (showing a tendency toward a negative correlation, although not statistically significant), which may reflect a diet-induced modulation of HPI axis activity. Such alterations may represent a physiological adaptation or a shift in stress sensitivity in fish chronically exposed to the supplement. *Crhbp* is considered an antagonist of *Crh*, as it inhibits activation of the *Crh* receptor (Ruiz-Jarabo et al., 2018), thereby finely modulating HPI axis activity through a dual regulatory role (Martos-Sitcha et al., 2019). This mechanism could contribute to reduced cortisol release, potentially mediated by the effects of the nutraceutical compound.

At the head kidney level, the main effector of the stress axis in fish (Gorissen and Flik, 2016), distinct expression patterns were observed. The gene *star*, which encodes the steroidogenic acute regulatory protein involved in cholesterol transport during cortisol synthesis (Arukwe, 2008), was significantly downregulated in fish fed the nutraceutical-enriched diet (GG) compared to the control. While stress typically induces *star* expression (Kusakabe et al., 2002; Castillo et al., 2008), it has been reported that diets rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids can modulate its expression (Martins et al., 2012), such as those present in the functional ingredient *LB-GreenGrape*. Similarly, although *cyp11b1*, which encodes 11 β -hydroxylase, the final enzyme in cortisol synthesis (Aluru and Vijayan, 2006), did not differ significantly among diets, its expression paralleled that of *star* within each dietary group, as reflected by their positive correlations. This co-expression pattern, previously described in this species (Simó-Mirabet et al., 2025), supports a modulatory effect of the nutraceutical. A comparable effect was reported by Caderno et al. (2025), where two microalgae-based nutraceutical compounds downregulated *cyp11b1* expression. Moreover, the discrepancy between pituitary signaling and the interrenal response, evidenced by the negative correlations between these genes and *pomca* and *pomcb* in the GG group (a pattern absent in the CT and PP groups), suggests a regulation of steroidogenesis at the peripheral level. These findings indicate that the nutraceutical may directly modulate interrenal function or interfere with *Acth* sensitivity, thereby influencing HPI axis dynamics while maintaining basal expression of central components.

Additionally, a similar co-expression pattern was observed between *hsd11b2* and *nr3c1*, with both genes being significantly upregulated in the PP group. *Hsd11b2* regulates the balance between active cortisol and its inactive form, cortisone (Nematollahi et al., 2012). Its upregulation may represent a compensatory mechanism to attenuate cortisol signaling at the interrenal level under nutritional stress (Flatt and Alderman, 2024), potentially contributing to the maintenance of cortisol homeostasis across dietary treatments. Such regulation could limit overactivation of glucocorticoid receptors encoded by *nr3c1*, thereby attenuating cortisol effects (Theodoridi et al., 2021), although in the PP group this effect may be less evident due to the parallel upregulation of *nr3c1*. Overall, these responses could also be modulated, at least in part, by the inclusion of the nutraceutical in the GG diet. In contrast, Caderno et al. (2025) reported marked dysregulation of the stress axis in juvenile *S. aurata* fed plant-based diets without biotechnological processing, including downregulation of *nr3c1*, elevated cortisol levels, and pronounced negative feedback along the HPI axis. In that study, this dysregulation extended to intermediary metabolism, with altered plasma and hepatic metabolite profiles, whereas metabolic parameters remained stable across diets in the present study. Taken together, these findings suggest that both enzymatic pre-treatment of plant ingredients and nutraceutical supplementation contribute to a more balanced regulation of the stress axis and intermediary metabolism, thereby

Fig. 6. Pearson correlation matrices showing relationships among gene expression along the hypothalamus-pituitary-interrenal (HPI) axis in gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) fed experimental diets for 84 days to apparent visual satiety (CT: control diet containing 20% FM; PP: diet with 60% replacement of FM by hydrolyzed plant protein; GG: PP diet supplemented with 2% *LB-GreenGrape*): (A) CT; (B) PP; (C) GG. Tissue abbreviations: H: Hypothalamus; P: Pituitary; HK: Head kidney. Asterisks indicate statistically significant correlations: $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**), and $p < 0.001$ (***).

Fig. 7. Intestinal and liver morphometric analyses in gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) fed experimental diets for 84 days to apparent visual satiety (CT, PP, and GG): (A) hepatocyte area (μm^2); (B) mucosal-to-submucosal surface ratio (MSR); (C) goblet cell density (GC mm^{-2}). Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM from 9 fish per experimental group. Additional methodological and statistical details are provided in Fig. 1.

Table 8Estimated effect of *LB-GreenGrape* inclusion on feed savings and overall feed cost balance for the production of one ton of farmed fish.

Experimental groups	Parameters						
	FE (kg fish/kg feed)	Total feed (kg feed/ton fish)	Feed vs. CT (kg feed/ton fish)	Additive use (kg/ton fish)	Additive cost ¹ (€/ton fish)	Feed cost ² (€/ton fish)	Balance ³ (€/ton fish)
CT	0.81	1240				1860	
PP	0.70	1430	190			2145	
GG	0.77	1300	60	26	134	2084	-61

FE: Feed efficiency.

Feed cost was estimated at €1.50 kg⁻¹.¹ The cost of *LB-GreenGrape* was €5.15 kg⁻¹.² For the GG diet, total cost was calculated as the sum of feed cost (€/ton fish) and additive cost (€/ton fish).³ Estimated as feed cost savings relative to the PP diet (€/ton fish).

helping to mitigate the physiological challenges typically associated with plant-based diets.

4.3. Histological and functional responses to nutritional impact

At the hepatic level, no significant alterations were detected in plasma enzymes or other metabolic and physiological hepatic parameters, suggesting the absence of overt liver dysfunction (Javed et al., 2016). However, hepatocyte area was increased in the PP group, consistent with previous studies linking this response to plant-based dietary formulations (Donadelli et al., 2024). Although hepatocyte enlargement has been associated with lipid or glycogen accumulation (Karatas et al., 2021), the absence of changes in related biochemical and somatic indices in the present study does not support a clear alteration in hepatic energy storage. In contrast, Caderno et al. (2025) reported increased glycogen concentration, elevated HSI values, and enhanced adipocyte deposition surrounding the intrahepatic exocrine pancreas in juvenile *S. aurata* fed plant-based diets without biotechnological processing. This discrepancy may indicate that enzymatic pre-treatment of plant ingredients modulates these responses. Collectively, these findings highlight the complex interplay among HSI, energy balance, nutraceutical composition, and ingredient processing.

At the intestinal level, fish fed the PP diet exhibited shorter intestines, whereas those fed the GG diet showed intestinal lengths comparable to the control (CT). Duque-Correa et al. (2024) noted that, although longer intestines are generally associated with less digestible diets, this pattern is not always consistent and reflects the still-limited understanding of the mechanisms underlying nutrient utilization in fish. The enzymatic biotechnological treatment of plant ingredients in the PP diet may have improved nutrient availability, thereby reducing the need for intestinal adaptation. In contrast, the inclusion of *LB-GreenGrape* appeared to counteract this effect, restoring intestinal length to control levels. Previous studies have reported intestinal elongation in *S. aurata* fed low levels of microalgal supplements in both FM/FO diets and plant-based diets without biotechnological processing (Perera et al., 2020; Caderno et al., 2025, respectively). Caderno et al. (2025) also reported that such intestinal elongation was associated with alterations in intestinal integrity, including separation between mucosa and submucosa layers, increased apparent permeability, and reduced trans-epithelial resistance. However, in other species such as *Seriola dumerili*, intestinal elongation has been reported even when plant-based diets were enzymatically processed (Molina-Roque et al., 2025), suggesting species-specific differences in intestinal plasticity. The observed reduction in intestinal length likely reflects a diet-induced morphological adaptation, probably linked to aquafeed composition and nutrient availability.

Morphometric analysis revealed no changes in MSR. Although ANF in plant-based diets can induce intestinal alterations, such as submucosal widening (Tran-Ngoc et al., 2019), the enzymatic biotechnological hydrolysis of plant ingredients, together with nutraceutical supplementation, appears to prevent these effects. The similar GC density

observed between the CT and PP groups supports this interpretation. GC density was significantly increased only in response to nutraceutical supplementation, suggesting a modulatory effect. While some studies have reported reduced GC numbers in gilthead seabream fed unprocessed plant-based diets or microalgae, associated with epithelial damage and impaired intestinal defense (Cerezuela et al., 2012; Caderno et al., 2025), others, such as Shi et al. (2021) in *Danio rerio*, have described opposite trends. Overall, the intestinal responses observed in this study highlight a complex interplay among ingredient composition, processing, and host physiology. In this context, the inclusion of hydrolyzed microalgae and *Albariño* grape marc extracts appears to modulate gut morphology in a manner that may support both structural homeostasis and increased resilience to pathogenic challenges.

5. Conclusions

The results of this study demonstrate that the combination of enzymatically treated plant proteins with the functional ingredient *LB-GreenGrape* represents a promising and sustainable nutritional strategy for aquaculture. Enzymatic treatment of plant-based ingredients improved the physiological response of fish, as reflected in a balanced metabolic and endocrine profile, without marked alterations in stress or tissue damage indicators. The inclusion of the nutraceutical further improved growth performance and physiological regulation, maintaining Gh/Igf axis signaling and modulating key stress-related genes, thereby restoring alterations induced by the high inclusion of plant-based ingredients that were not fully alleviated by enzymatic processing. Additionally, *LB-GreenGrape* supplementation contributed to improved intestinal integrity and preserved hepatic stability, as evidenced by increased goblet cell density and the absence of adverse morphological or biochemical alterations. Overall, these findings support the potential of *LB-GreenGrape* to mitigate the limitations associated with plant-based diets, promoting a more balanced physiological and productive profile and contributing to the development of functional and sustainable aquafeeds.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

A. Caderno: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **V. de las Heras:** Methodology, Investigation. **M. Román-Arias:** Methodology, Investigation. **M. Oliva:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **J. Román-Padilla:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **J.M. Mancera:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition. **F.J. Alarcón-López:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition. **G. Martínez-Rodríguez:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **J.A. Martos-Sitcha:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) did not use any AI and AI-assisted technologies.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2026.744020>.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are not deposited in an official repository but are available upon request.

References

- Ahmad, A., Hassan, S.W., Banat, F., 2022. An overview of microalgae biomass as a sustainable aquaculture feed ingredient: food security and circular economy. *Bioengineered* 13 (4), 9521–9547. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21655979.2022.2061148>.
- Aluru, N., Vijayan, M.M., 2006. Aryl hydrocarbon receptor activation impairs cortisol response to stress in rainbow trout by disrupting the rate-limiting steps in steroidogenesis. *Endocrinology* 147 (4), 1895–1903. <https://doi.org/10.1210/en.2005-1143>.
- APROMAR, 2024. *La acuicultura en España 2024*. APROMAR.
- Arukwe, A., 2008. Steroidogenic acute regulatory (StAR) protein and cholesterol side-chain cleavage (p450 scc)-regulated steroidogenesis as an organ-specific molecular and cellular target for endocrine disrupting chemicals in fish. *Cell Biol. Toxicol.* 24, 527–540. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10565-008-9069-7>.
- Barbacariu, C.A., Dirvari, L., Șerban, D.A., Rîmbu, C.M., Horhogea, C.E., Dumitru, G., Todirașcu-Ciornea, E., Lungoci, C., Burducea, M., 2024. Evaluating the use of grape pomace in *Cyprinus carpio* nutrition: effects on growth, biochemistry, meat quality, microbiota, and oxidative status. *Fishes* 9 (6), 219. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fishes9060219>.
- Benedito-Palos, L., Saera-Vila, A., Calduch-Giner, J.A., Kaushik, S., Pérez-Sánchez, J., 2007. Combined replacement of fish meal and oil in practical diets for fast growing juveniles of gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata* L.): networking of systemic and local components of GH/IGF axis. *Aquaculture* 267 (1–4), 199–212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2007.01.011>.
- Benedito-Palos, L., Ballester-Lozano, G.F., Simó, P., Karalazos, V., Ortiz, Á., Calduch-Giner, J., Pérez-Sánchez, J., 2016. Lasting effects of butyrate and low FM/FO diets on growth performance, blood haematology/biochemistry and molecular growth-related markers in gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*). *Aquaculture* 454, 8–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2015.12.008>.
- Bertucci, J.I., Blanco, A.M., Sundararajan, L., Rajeswari, J.J., Velasco, C., Unniappan, S., 2019. Nutrient regulation of endocrine factors influencing feeding and growth in fish. *Front. Endocrinol.* 10, 83. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2019.00083>.
- Caderno, A., Simó-Mirabet, P., García-Zara, M., Martos-Sitcha, J.A., 2024. Short-term starvation and refeeding in the greater amberjack (*Seriola dumerili*, Risso 1810): new insights on physiological and metabolic traits. *Aquacult. Rep.* 39, 102403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqrep.2024.102403>.
- Caderno, A., Oliva, M., Barranco, I., Astola, A., Fuentes, J., Alarcón-López, F.J., Mancera, J.M., Martos-Sitcha, J.A., 2025. Microalgae-derived feed additives improve physiological health, intestinal integrity, and welfare in juvenile gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) fed plant-based diets. *Aquaculture*, 742873. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2025.742873>.
- Caderno, A., Tang, P., de Las Heras, V., Gharbi, N., Alarcón-López, F.J., Mancera, J.M., Martos-Sitcha, J.A., Gilannejad, N., 2026. Spatiotemporal characterization of ghrelin and cholecystokinin levels in the gastrointestinal tract of juvenile *Sparus aurata*: effects of feeding status and diet composition. *Front. Endocrinol.* 17, 1734169. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2026.1734169>.
- Canosa, L.F., Bertucci, J.I., 2023. The effect of environmental stressors on growth in fish and its endocrine control. *Front. Endocrinol.* 14, 1109461. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2023.1109461>.
- Cao, Y., Xu, M., Lu, J., Cai, G., 2024. Simultaneous microbial fermentation and enzymolysis: a biotechnology strategy to improve the nutritional and functional quality of soybean meal. *Food Rev. Int.* 40 (5), 1296–1311. <https://doi.org/10.1080/87559129.2023.2212048>.
- Carbajal, A., Reyes-López, F.E., Tallo-Parra, O., Lopez-Bejar, M., Tort, L., 2019. Comparative assessment of cortisol in plasma, skin mucus and scales as a measure of the hypothalamic-pituitary-interrenal axis activity in fish. *Aquaculture* 506, 410–416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2019.04.005>.
- Castillo, J., Castellana, B., Acerete, L., Planas, J.V., Goetz, F.W., Mackenzie, S., Tort, L., 2008. Stress-induced regulation of steroidogenic acute regulatory protein expression in head kidney of gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*). *J. Endocrinol.* 196 (2), 313–320. <https://doi.org/10.1677/JOE-07-0440>.
- Cerezuela, R., Fumana, M., Tapia-Paniagua, S.T., Meseguer, J., Morínigo, M.Á., Esteban, M.Á., 2012. Histological alterations and microbial ecology of the intestine in gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata* L.) fed dietary probiotics and microalgae. *Cell Tissue Res.* 350, 477–489. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00441-012-1495-4>.
- Colombo, S.M., 2020. Physiological considerations in shifting carnivorous fishes to plant-based diets. In: Benfey, T.J., Farrell, A.P., Brauner, C.J. (Eds.), *Fish Physiology*, 38. Academic Press, pp. 53–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.fp.2020.09.002>.
- Company, R., Astola, A., Pendón, C., Valdivia, M.M., Pérez-Sánchez, J., 2001. Somatotrophic regulation of fish growth and adiposity: growth hormone (GH) and somatotrophic (SL) relationship. *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. C Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 130 (4), 435–445. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1532-0456\(01\)00269-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1532-0456(01)00269-1).
- Contreras, M.M., Romero-García, J.M., López-Linares, J.C., Romero, I., Castro, E., 2022. Residues from grapevine and wine production as feedstock for a biorefinery. *Food Bioprod. Process.* 134, 56–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbp.2022.05.005>.
- de Celis, S.V.R., Rojas, P., Gómez-Requeni, P., Albalat, A., Gutiérrez, J., Médale, F., Kaushik, S.J., Navarro, I., Pérez-Sánchez, J., 2004. Nutritional assessment of somatotrophic function in gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*): concurrent changes in somatotrophic axis and pancreatic hormones. *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. A Mol. Integr. Physiol.* 138 (4), 533–542. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpb.2004.06.007>.
- Deng, L., Zhang, W.M., Lin, H.R., Cheng, C.H., 2004. Effects of food deprivation on expression of growth hormone receptor and proximate composition in liver of black seabream *acanthopagrus schlegelii*. *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. B: Biochem. Mol. Biol.* 137 (4), 421–432. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpc.2004.01.008>.
- Desai, A.R., Links, M.G., Collins, S.A., Mansfield, G.S., Drew, M.D., Van Kessel, A.G., Hill, J.E., 2012. Effects of plant-based diets on the distal gut microbiome of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). *Aquaculture* 350, 134–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2012.04.005>.
- Dhanasiri, A.K., Johnny, A., Xue, X., Berge, G.M., Bøgevik, A.S., Rise, M.L., Fæste, C.K., Fernandes, J.M., 2020. Plant-based diets induce transcriptomic changes in muscle of zebrafish and Atlantic salmon. *Front. Genet.* 11, 575237. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgen.2020.575237>.
- Diógenes, A.F., Basto, A., Estevão-Rodrigues, T.T., Moutinho, S., Aires, T., Oliva-Teles, A., Peres, H., 2019. Soybean meal replacement by corn distillers dried grains with solubles (DDGS) and exogenous non-starch polysaccharidases supplementation in diets for gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) juveniles. *Aquaculture* 500, 435–442. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2018.10.035>.
- Donadelli, V., Di Marco, P., Mandich, A., Finoia, M.G., Cardinaletti, G., Petochi, T., Longobardi, A., Tibaldi, E., Marino, G., 2024. Effects of dietary plant protein replacement with insect and poultry by-product meals on the liver health and serum metabolites of sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) and sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*). *Animals* 14 (2), 241. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani14020241>.
- Duan, C., 1998. Nutritional and developmental regulation of insulin-like growth factors in fish. *J. Nutr.* 128 (2), 306S–314S. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/128.2.306S>.
- Duque-Correa, M.J., Clements, K.D., Meloro, C., Ronco, F., Boila, A., Indermaur, A., Salzburger, W., Clauss, M., Clauss, M., 2024. Diet and habitat as determinants of intestine length in fishes. *Rev. Fish Biol. Fish.* 34 (3), 1017–1034. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11160-024-09853-3>.
- Ellis, T., Yildiz, H.Y., López-Olmeda, J., Spedicato, M.T., Tort, L., Øverli, Ø., Martins, C.I., 2012. Cortisol and finfish welfare. *Fish Physiol. Biochem.* 38, 163–188. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10695-011-9568-y>.
- Encarnação, P., 2016. Functional feed additives in aquaculture feeds. In: Nates, S.F. (Ed.), *Aquafeed Formulation*. Academic Press, pp. 217–237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-800873-7.00005-1>.

- Eppler, E., Shved, N., Moret, O., Reinecke, M., 2007. IGF-I is distinctly located in the bony fish pituitary as revealed for *Oreochromis niloticus*, the Nile tilapia, using real-time RT-PCR, in situ hybridisation and immunohistochemistry. *Gen. Comp. Endocrinol.* 150 (1), 87–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ygcen.2006.07.013>.
- Fernández-Alacid, L., Sanahuja, I., Ordóñez-Grande, B., Sánchez-Nuño, S., Viscor, G., Gisbert, E., Herrera, M., Ibarz, A., 2018. Skin mucus metabolites in response to physiological challenges: a valuable non-invasive method to study teleost marine species. *Sci. Total Environ.* 644, 1323–1335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.07.083>.
- Fernández-Alacid, L., Sanahuja, I., Ordóñez-Grande, B., Sánchez-Nuño, S., Herrera, M., Ibarz, A., 2019. Skin mucus metabolites and cortisol in meagre fed acute stress-attenuating diets: correlations between plasma and mucus. *Aquaculture* 499, 185–194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2018.09.039>.
- Flatt, E.E., Alderman, S.L., 2024. 11 β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 2 may mediate the stress-specific effects of cortisol on brain cell proliferation in adult zebrafish (*Danio rerio*). *J. Exp. Biol.* 227 (16), jeb248020. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.248020>.
- Flores-Moreno, S., Vizcaíno, A.J., Sáez, M.I., Macías-Vidal, J., Martínez, T.F., Martos-Sitcha, J.A., Alarcón-López, F.J., 2024. Effects of phytase and microalgae supplementation on the utilization of aquafeeds for European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) formulated with a high inclusion level of plant protein. *Aquac. Res.* 2024 (1), 4775004. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2024/4775004>.
- Fox, B.K., Riley, L.G., Hirano, T., Grau, E.G., 2006. Effects of fasting on growth hormone, growth hormone receptor, and insulin-like growth factor-I axis in seawater-acclimated tilapia, *Oreochromis mossambicus*. *Gen. Comp. Endocrinol.* 148 (3), 340–347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ygcen.2006.04.007>.
- Francis, G., Makkar, H.P., Becker, K., 2001. Antinutritional factors present in plant-derived alternate fish feed ingredients and their effects in fish. *Aquaculture* 199 (3–4), 197–227. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486\(01\)00526-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486(01)00526-9).
- Galafat, A., Vizcaíno, A.J., Sáez, M.I., Martínez, T.F., Arizcun, M., Chaves-Pozo, E., Alarcón, F.J., 2022. Assessment of dietary inclusion of crude or hydrolysed arthrospira platensis biomass in starter diets for gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*). *Aquaculture* 548, 737680. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2021.737680>.
- García de la Serrana, D., Macqueen, D.J., 2018. Insulin-like growth factor-binding proteins of teleost fishes. *Front. Endocrinol.* 9, 80. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2018.00080>.
- Gómez-Requeni, P., Mingarro, M., Kirchner, S., Calduch-Giner, J.A., Médale, F., Corraze, G., Panserat, S., Martin, S.A.M., Houlihan, D.F., Kaushik, S.J., Pérez-Sánchez, J., 2003. Effects of dietary amino acid profile on growth performance, key metabolic enzymes and somatotrophic axis responsiveness of gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*). *Aquaculture* 220 (1–4), 749–767. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486\(02\)00654-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486(02)00654-3).
- Gómez-Requeni, P., Mingarro, M., Calduch-Giner, J.A., Médale, F., Martin, S.A.M., Houlihan, D.F., Kaushik, S., Pérez-Sánchez, J., 2004. Protein growth performance, amino acid utilisation and somatotrophic axis responsiveness to fish meal replacement by plant protein sources in gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*). *Aquaculture* 232 (1–4), 493–510. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486\(03\)00532-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486(03)00532-5).
- Gómez-Requeni, P., Kraemer, M.N., Canosa, L.F., 2019. The dietary lipid content affects the tissue gene expression of muscle growth biomarkers and the GH/IGF system of pejerrey (*Odontesthes bonariensis*) juveniles. *Fishes* 4 (3), 37. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fishes4030037>.
- Gorissen, M., Flik, G., 2016. The endocrinology of the stress response in fish: An adaptation-physiological view. In: Farrell, A.P., Brauner, C.J. (Eds.), *Fish Physiology*, 35. Academic Press, pp. 75–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-802728-8.00003-5>.
- Gule, T.T., Geremew, A., 2022. Dietary strategies for better utilization of aquafeeds in tilapia farming. *Aquac. Nutr.* 2022, 9463307. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/9463307>.
- Hassaan, M.S., El-Sayed, A.I.M., Soltan, M.A., Iraqi, M.M., Goda, A.M., Davies, S.J., El-Haroun, E.R., Ramadan, H.A., 2019. Partial dietary fish meal replacement with cotton seed meal and supplementation with exogenous protease alters growth, feed performance, hematological indices and associated gene expression markers (GH, IGF-I) for Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Aquaculture* 503, 282–292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2019.01.009>.
- Hevroy, E.M., El-Mowafi, A., Taylor, R., Norberg, B., Espe, M., 2008. Effects of a high plant protein diet on the somatotrophic system and cholecystokinin in Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar* L.). *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. A Mol. Integr. Physiol.* 151 (4), 621–627. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpa.2008.07.026>.
- Hossain, M.S., Small, B.C., Kumar, V., Hardy, R., 2024. Utilization of functional feed additives to produce cost-effective, ecofriendly aquafeeds high in plant-based ingredients. *Rev. Aquac.* 16 (1), 121–153. <https://doi.org/10.1111/raq.12824>.
- Hua, K., Cobcroft, J.M., Cole, A., Condon, K., Jerry, D.R., Mangott, A., Praeger, C., Vucko, M.J., Zeng, C., Zenger, K., Strugnell, J.M., 2019. The future of aquatic protein: implications for protein sources in aquaculture diets. *One Earth* 1 (3), 316–329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2019.10.018>.
- Huy, M., Vatland, A.K., Kumar, G., 2022. Nutraceutical productions from microalgal derived compounds via circular bioeconomy perspective. *Bioresour. Technol.* 347, 126575. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2021.126575>.
- Idenyi, J.N., Eya, J.C., Nwankwegu, A.S., Nwoba, E.G., 2022. Aquaculture sustainability through alternative dietary ingredients: microalgal value-added products. *Eng. Microbiol.* 2 (4), 100049. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engmic.2022.100049>.
- Javed, M., Ahmad, I., Ahmad, A., Usmani, N., Ahmad, M., 2016. Studies on the alterations in haematological indices, micronuclei induction and pathological marker enzyme activities in *Channa punctatus* (spotted snakehead) exposed to thermal power plant effluent. *SpringerPlus* 5, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40064-016-2478-9>.
- Karatas, T., Onalan, S., Yildirim, S., 2021. Effects of prolonged fasting on levels of metabolites, oxidative stress, immune-related gene expression, histopathology, and DNA damage in the liver and muscle tissues of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). *Fish Physiol. Biochem.* 47 (4), 1119–1132. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10695-021-00949-2>.
- Kaur, S., Das, M., 2011. Functional foods: an overview. *Food Sci. Biotechnol.* 20, 861–875. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10068-011-0121-7>.
- Kepler, D., Decker, K., 1974. Glycogen determination with amyloglucosidase. In: Bergmeyer, H.U. (Ed.), *Methods of Enzymatic Analysis*, pp. 127–131.
- Khieokhajokhet, A., Kaneko, G., Hirano, Y., Wang, L., Ushio, H., 2016. Different effects of growth hormone and fasting on the induction patterns of two hormone-sensitive lipase genes in red seabream (*Pagrus major*). *Gen. Comp. Endocrinol.* 236, 121–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ygcen.2016.06.025>.
- Krogdahl, Å., Penn, M., Thorsen, J., Refstie, S., Bakke, A.M., 2010. Important antinutrients in plant feedstuffs for aquaculture: an update on recent findings regarding responses in salmonids. *Aquac. Res.* 41 (3), 333–344. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2109.2009.02426.x>.
- Kusakabe, M., Todo, T., McQuillan, H.J., Goetz, F.W., Young, G., 2002. Characterization and expression of steroidogenic acute regulatory protein and MLN64 cDNAs in trout. *Endocrinology* 143 (6), 2062–2070. <https://doi.org/10.1210/endo.143.6.8672>.
- Le Boucher, R., Quillet, E., Vandeputte, M., Lecalvez, J.M., Goardon, L., Chatain, B., Médale, F., Dupont-Nivet, M., 2011. Plant-based diet in rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss* Walbaum): are there genotype-diet interactions for main production traits when fish are fed marine vs. plant-based diets from the first meal? *Aquaculture* 321 (1–2), 41–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2011.08.010>.
- Livak, K.J., Schmittgen, T.D., 2001. Analysis of relative gene expression data using real-time quantitative PCR and the 2 $^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$ method. *Methods* 25 (4), 402–408. <https://doi.org/10.1006/meth.2001.1262>.
- Martínez-Antequera, F.P., López-Ruiz, R., Martos-Sitcha, J.A., Mancera, J.M., Moyano, F. J., 2023. Assessing differences in the bioaccessibility of phenolics present in two wine by-products using an *in-vitro* model of fish digestion. *Front. Veterin. Sci.* 10, 1151045. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2023.1151045>.
- Martins, D.A., Rocha, F., Martínez-Rodríguez, G., Bell, G., Morais, S., Castanheira, F., Bandarra, N., Coutinho, J., Yúfera, M., Conceição, L.E., 2012. Teleost fish larvae adapt to dietary arachidonic acid supply through modulation of the expression of lipid metabolism and stress response genes. *Br. J. Nutr.* 108 (5), 864–874. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007114511006143>.
- Martoja, R., Martoja-Pierson, M., 1970. *Técnicas de Histología Animal*.
- Martos-Sitcha, J.A., Cádiz, L., Gozdowska, M., Kulczykowska, E., Martínez-Rodríguez, G., Mancera, J.M., 2019. Arginine vasotocin and cortisol co-regulate vasotocinergic, isotocinergic, stress, and thyroid pathways in the gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*). *Front. Physiol.* 10, 261. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2019.00261>.
- Men, K., Ai, Q., Mai, K., Xu, W., Zhang, Y., Zhou, H., 2014. Effects of dietary corn gluten meal on growth, digestion and protein metabolism in relation to IGF-I gene expression of Japanese seabass, *Lateolabrax japonicus*. *Aquaculture* 428, 303–309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2014.03.028>.
- Midhun, S.J., Arun, D., 2023. Alternative feed technology in aquaculture. In: Midhun, S. J., Arun, D. (Eds.), *Recent Advances in Aquaculture Microbial Technology*. Academic Press, pp. 291–306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-90261-8.00007-9>.
- Molina-Roque, L., Simó-Mirabet, P., Barany, A., Caderno, A., Navarro-Guillén, C., Galafat, A., Torres, M., Fuentes, J., Mancera, J.M., Perera, E., Alarcón-López, F.J., Martos-Sitcha, J.A., 2025. Enzymatic treatment of plant proteins in combination with algae-based nutraceutical inclusion in aquafeeds improves growth performance and physiological traits in the greater amberjack (*Seriola dumerili*). *Aquaculture* 598, 742012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2024.742012>.
- Nagarajan, D., Varjani, S., Lee, D.J., Chang, J.S., 2021. Sustainable aquaculture and animal feed from microalgae – nutritive value and techno-functional components. *Renew. Sust. Energ. Rev.* 150, 111549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111549>.
- Nematollahi, M.A., van Pelt-Heerschap, H., Atsma, W., Komen, J., 2012. High levels of corticosterone, and gene expression of *star*, *cyp17a2*, *hsd3b*, *cyp21*, *hsd11b2* during acute stress in common carp with interrenal hyperplasia. *Gen. Comp. Endocrinol.* 176 (2), 252–258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ygcen.2012.01.023>.
- Omlin, T., Weber, J.M., 2010. Hypoxia stimulates lactate disposal in rainbow trout. *J. Exp. Biol.* 213 (22), 3802–3809. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.048512>.
- Perelló-Amorós, M., García-Pérez, I., Sánchez-Moya, A., Innamorati, A., Vélez, E.J., Achaerandio, I., Pujolà, M., Calduch-Giner, J., Pérez-Sánchez, J., Fernández-Borrás, J., Blasco, J., Gutiérrez, J., 2021. Diet and exercise modulate GH-IGFs axis, proteolytic markers and myogenic regulatory factors in juveniles of gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*). *Animals* 11 (8), 2182. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani11082182>.
- Perera, E., Sánchez-Ruiz, D., Sáez, M.I., Galafat, A., Barany, A., Fernández-Castro, M., Vizcaíno, A.J., Fuentes, J., Francisco-Martínez, T., Mancera, J.M., Alarcón, F.J., Martos-Sitcha, J.A., 2020. Low dietary inclusion of nutraceuticals from microalgae improves feed efficiency and modifies intermediary metabolisms in gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*). *Sci. Rep.* 10 (1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-75693-3>.
- Pérez-Sánchez, J., Le Bail, P.Y., 1999. Growth hormone axis as marker of nutritional status and growth performance in fish. *Aquaculture* 177 (1–4), 117–128. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486\(99\)00073-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486(99)00073-3).
- Pérez-Sánchez, J., Martí-Palanca, H., Kaushik, S.J., 1995. Ration size and protein intake affect circulating growth hormone concentration, hepatic growth hormone binding and plasma insulin-like growth factor-I immunoreactivity in a marine teleost, the gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*). *J. Nutr.* 125 (3), 546–552. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/125.3.546>.
- Pérez-Sánchez, J., Simó-Mirabet, P., Naya-Català, F., Martos-Sitcha, J.A., Perera, E., Bermejo-Nogales, A., Benedito-Palos, L., Calduch-Giner, J.A., 2018. Somatotrophic

- axis regulation unravels the differential effects of nutritional and environmental factors in growth performance of marine farmed fishes. *Front. Endocrinol.* 9, 687. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2018.00687>.
- Pfaffl, M.W., 2001. A new mathematical model for relative quantification in real-time RT-PCR. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 29 (9), e45. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/29.9.e45>.
- Picha, M.E., Turano, M.J., Beckman, B.R., Borski, R.J., 2008. Endocrine biomarkers of growth and applications to aquaculture: a mini review of growth hormone, insulin-like growth factor (IGF)-I, and IGF-binding proteins as potential growth indicators in fish. *N. Am. J. Aquac.* 70 (2), 196–211. <https://doi.org/10.1577/A07-038.1>.
- Prabu, E., Rajagopalsamy, C.B.T., Ahilan, B., Santhakumar, R., Jeevagan, I.J.M.A., Renuhadevi, M., 2017. An overview of anti-nutritional factors in fish feed ingredients and their effects in fish. *J. Aquac. Tropics* 32 (1–2), 149.
- Quagliardi, M., Frapiccini, E., Marini, M., Panfili, M., Santanatoglia, A., Nguiefang, M.L. K., Roncarati, A., Vittori, S., Borsetta, G., 2024. Use of grape by-products in aquaculture: new frontiers for a circular economy application. *Heliyon* 10 (5), e27443. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e27443>.
- Reinecke, M., Björnsson, B.T., Dickhoff, W.W., McCormick, S.D., Navarro, I., Power, D. M., Gutiérrez, J., 2005. Growth hormone and insulin-like growth factors in fish: where we are and where to go. *Gen. Comp. Endocrinol.* 142 (1–2), 20–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ygcen.2005.01.016>.
- Reis, B., Ramos-Pinto, L., Martos-Sitcha, J.A., Machado, M., Azeredo, R., Fernández-Boo, S., Engrola, S., Unamunzaga, S., Calduch-Giner, J., Conceição, L.E.C., Silva, T., Dias, J., Costas, B., Pérez-Sánchez, J., 2021. Health status in gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) juveniles fed diets devoid of fishmeal and supplemented with *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*. *J. Appl. Physiol.* 33, 979–996. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10811-021-02377-4>.
- Reverter, M., Tapissier-Bontemps, N., Sarter, S., Sasal, P., Caruso, D., 2021. Moving towards more sustainable aquaculture practices: a meta-analysis on the potential of plant-enriched diets to improve fish growth, immunity and disease resistance. *Rev. Aquac.* 13 (1), 537–555. <https://doi.org/10.1111/raq.12485>.
- Rolland, M., Dalsgaard, J., Holm, J., Gómez-Requeni, P., Skov, P.V., 2015. Dietary methionine level affects growth performance and hepatic gene expression of GH-IGF system and protein turnover regulators in rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) fed plant protein-based diets. *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. B: Biochem. Mol. Biol.* 181, 33–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpb.2014.11.009>.
- Ruiz-Jarabo, I., Martos-Sitcha, J.A., Barragán-Méndez, C., Martínez-Rodríguez, G., Mancera, J.M., Arjona, F.J., 2018. Gene expression of thyrotropin- and corticotrophin-releasing hormones is regulated by environmental salinity in the euryhaline teleost *Sparus aurata*. *Fish Physiol. Biochem.* 44 (2), 615–628. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10695-017-0457-x>.
- Saera-Vila, A., Calduch-Giner, J.A., Pérez-Sánchez, J., 2005. Duplication of growth hormone receptor (GHR) in fish genome: gene organization and transcriptional regulation of GHR type I and II in gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*). *Gen. Comp. Endocrinol.* 142 (1–2), 193–203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ygcen.2004.11.005>.
- Saera-Vila, A., Calduch-Giner, J.A., Prunet, P., Pérez-Sánchez, J., 2009. Dynamics of liver GH/IGF axis and selected stress markers in juvenile gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) exposed to acute confinement: differential stress response of growth hormone receptors. *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. A Mol. Integr. Physiol.* 154 (2), 197–203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpa.2009.06.004>.
- Sánchez-Moya, A., Balbuena-Pecino, S., Vélez, E.J., Perelló-Amorós, M., García-Meílán, I., Fontanillas, R., Calduch-Giner, J.A., Pérez-Sánchez, J., Fernández-Borràs, J., Blasco, J., Gutiérrez, J., 2023. Cysteamine improves growth and the GH/IGF axis in gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*): in vivo and in vitro approaches. *Front. Endocrinol.* 14, 1211470. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2023.1211470>.
- Sarker, P.K., 2023. Microorganisms in fish feeds, technological innovations, and key strategies for sustainable aquaculture. *Microorganisms* 11 (2), 439. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms11020439>.
- Shi, Y., Cao, X., Ye, Z., Xu, Y., Wang, Y., Li, Z., Hang, W., He, N., 2021. Role of dietary *Schizochytrium* sp. in improving disease resistance of zebrafish through metabolic and microbial analysis. *Aquaculture* 539, 736631. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2021.736631>.
- Shinde, S.V., Sawant, S., Rathod, S.S., Patekar, P., Sheikh, S., Narsale, S., Sukhdhane, K., 2024. Strategic nutraceutical approaches for enhancing fisheries and aquaculture: a comprehensive review. *Int. J. Adv. Biotechnol. Res.* 8 (3), 104–110. <https://doi.org/10.33545/26174693.2024.v8.i3Sb.701>.
- Shved, N., Berishvili, G., Mazel, P., Baroiller, J.F., Eppler, E., 2011. Growth hormone (GH) treatment acts on the endocrine and autocrine/paracrine GH/IGF-axis and on TNF- α expression in bony fish pituitary and immune organs. *Fish Shellfish Immunol.* 31 (6), 944–952. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fsi.2011.08.012>.
- Simó-Mirabet, P., Caderno, A., Flores-Llano, M.J., da Silva, E.G., Schoenau, W., Baldisserotto, B., Martínez-Rodríguez, G., Mancera, J.M., Martos-Sitcha, J.A., 2025. Evaluation of the sedative effect of limonene to reduce stress during transportation of gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*). *Biology* 14 (2), 115. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology14020115>.
- Sissener, N.H., Hemre, G.I., Espe, M., Sanden, M., Torstensen, B.E., Hevrøy, E.M., 2013. Effects of plant-based diets on glucose and amino acid metabolism, leptin, ghrelin and GH-IGF system regulation in Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar* L.). *Aquac. Nutr.* 19 (3), 399–412. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2095.2012.00971.x>.
- Stevens, A., 1982. The haematoxylins. In: Bancroft, J.D., Stevens, A. (Eds.), *The Theory and Practice of Histological Techniques*, pp. 109–121.
- Theodoridi, A., Dinarello, A., Badenetti, L., Pavlidis, M., Dalla Valle, L., Tsalafouta, A., 2021. Knockout of the *hsd11b2* gene extends the cortisol stress response in both zebrafish larvae and adults. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 22 (22), 12525. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms222212525>.
- Tran-Ngoc, K.T., Haidar, M.N., Roem, A.J., Sendão, J., Verreth, J.A., Schrama, J.W., 2019. Effects of feed ingredients on nutrient digestibility, nitrogen/energy balance and morphology changes in the intestine of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Aquac. Res.* 50 (9), 2577–2590. <https://doi.org/10.1111/are.14214>.
- Tsalafouta, A., Sarropoulou, E., Papandroulakis, N., Pavlidis, M., 2018. Characterization and expression dynamics of key genes involved in the gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) cortisol stress response during early ontogeny. *Mar. Biotechnol.* 20, 611–622. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10126-018-9833-5>.
- Tu, Y., Xie, S., Han, D., Yang, Y., Jin, J., Liu, H., Zhu, X., 2015. Growth performance, digestive enzyme, transaminase and GH-IGF-I axis gene responsiveness to different dietary protein levels in broodstock allogeny genetic gibel carp (*Carassius auratus gibelio*) CAS III. *Aquaculture* 446, 290–297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2015.05.003>.
- Uchida, K., Kajimura, S., Riley, L.G., Hirano, T., Aida, K., Grau, E.G., 2003. Effects of fasting on growth hormone/insulin-like growth factor I axis in the tilapia, *Oreochromis mossambicus*. *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. A Mol. Integr. Physiol.* 134 (2), 429–439. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1095-6433\(02\)00318-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1095-6433(02)00318-5).
- Vizcaíno, A.J., Sáez, M.I., Galafat, A., Galindo-Melero, R., Perera, E., Casal-Porras, I., Zubía, E., Vega, J., Figueroa, F.L., Martínez, T.F., Martos-Sitcha, J.A., Alarcón, F.J., 2024. Effects of feeding european seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) juveniles with crude, hydrolysed and fermented biomass of the invasive macroalga rugulopterix okamuræ (Ochrophyta). *Aquacult. Rep.* 34, 101877. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqrep.2023.101877>.
- Wong, A.O., Zhou, H., Jiang, Y., Ko, W.K., 2006. Feedback regulation of growth hormone synthesis and secretion in fish and the emerging concept of intrapituitary feedback loop. *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. A Mol. Integr. Physiol.* 144 (3), 284–305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpa.2005.11.021>.
- Yang, H., Li, Y., Wang, G., Xie, J., Kaneko, G., Yu, E., 2023. Dietary grape seed proanthocyanidin extract improved the chemical composition, antioxidant capacity, myofiber growth and flesh quality of Nile tilapia muscle. *Aquacult. Rep.* 33, 101878. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqrep.2023.101878>.